

Validation of wind farm parametrization in WRF using wind farm data

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This report is submitted as partial fulfillment of the requirements for graduation in the above education at the Technical University of Denmark.

DTU Wind Energy is a department of the Technical University of Denmark with a unique integration of research, education, innovation and public/private sector consulting in the field of wind energy. Our activities develop new opportunities and technology for the global and Danish exploitation of wind energy. Research focuses on key technical-scientific fields, which are central for the development, innovation and use of wind energy and provides the basis for advanced education at the education.

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Preface

This thesis investigates wind resources and the impact of upstream wind farms. The objective is to validate a parametrisation which models the upstream wind farms. The project is conducted in order to fulfil the requirements for graduating from the Technical University of Denmark for the master of science degree in Wind Energy. The project has been performed in collaboration with Ørsted Wind Power and DTU Wind Energy. Ørsted has provided data from their wind farms in the Irish Sea for the analysis.

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Abstract

Offshore wind energy continues to grow in both existing and new markets. With the increasing amount of installed wind energy, offshore wind farms have started to be built in closer proximity to each other. This complicates the process of estimating the annual energy production (AEP) as the wind resources can be affected by wakes of neighbouring wind farms. This study is focused on estimating and validating wind resources close to other wind farms.

The Weather Research & Forecasting (WRF) model was used to evaluate wind resources in a part of the Irish Sea with six wind farms. The wind farms were modelled with the Explicit Wake Parametrisation (EWP). Wind farm data (SCADA) has been used to validate the wind resources.

A grid resolution study utilising both the EWP and Fitch parametrisation scheme was performed, where the Fitch parametrisation showed weaker wake effects.

The computed wind resources predicted a minimum wind farm efficiency down to 82.6% for winds affected by neighbouring wind farms. In the same wind direction range, SCADA observed a minimum efficiency of 66.9%. The relative decrease in efficiency for WRF and SCADA proved to be very close. For WRF, the maximum relative change was 22.9% compared to when not including the upstream wind farms, while SCADA observed a maximum relative change in efficiency of 28.3% compared to before the upstream wind farms were operational.

The software Wind Atlas and Analysis and Application Program (WAsP) was used to estimate the net AEP, which was predicted to decrease by 3.9%, when including the upstream wind farms in the wind resource assessment.

WRF predicted the power production between two turbines in the same wind farm to differ by 32.9%, which was ascribed to external wake effects. The same turbine evaluation from SCADA was 50%.

In general, the wind resources calculated by WRF underestimated the impact of the wind farm wakes but the tendency was depicted accurately compared to SCADA. The wind farm wake direction was especially predicted accurately with respect to SCADA data.

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Abbreviations

AEP	Annual energy production
ARW	Advanced Research WRF
BOW	Barrow offshore wind farm
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasting
ERA5	ECMWF ReAnalysis v5
EWP	Explicit wake parametrisation
DTU	Technical University of Denmark
LES	Large eddy simulations
NEWA	New European Wind Atlas
NW	North-West
NWP	Numerical weather prediction model
OOWF	Ormonde offshore wind farm
OSTIA	Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Sea Ice Analysis
PBL	Planetary boundary layer
RANS	Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
SCADA	Supervisory control and data acquisition
SE	South-East
SF	Shell Flats meteorological mast
SF50m	Shell Flats 50 m meteorological mast
SF80m	Shell Flats 80 m meteorological mast
TKE	Turbulent kinetic energy
WAsP	Wind Atlas and Analysis and Application Program
WDS	West of Duddon Sands
WF	Wind farm
WOW01	Walney 1 / Walney Phase 1
WOW02	Walney 2 / Walney Phase 2
WOW03	Walney 3 / Walney Phase 3
WOW04	Walney 4 / Walney Phase 4
WRF	Weather Research & Forecasting model

Nomenclature & Notation

Latin symbols

a	Axial induction factor
A	Area
C_1, C_2	Constants
C_P	Specific heat
C_T	Thrust coefficient
D	Rotor diameter
e	Turbulent kinetic energy
f_{d_i}	Force exerted by wind turbine
g	Gravitational acceleration
h	Hub height
k	Wake decay coefficient
K	Turbulence diffusion coefficient
ℓ	Length travelled by wake
L	Obukhov length
N	Number of samples
N_t	Number of turbines
N_x, N_y	Number of cells in x and y direction
p	Pressure
p_b	Turbulent buoyant production
p_s	Turbulent shear production
p_t	Turbulence induced by a turbine
P	Power
PH	Perturbation geopotential
PHB	Basic state geopotential
r	Wake radius unless otherwise stated
r_0	Rotor radius
Ri	Gradient Richardson number
Ri_B	Bulk Richardson number
t	Time
T	Temperature unless otherwise stated
$u(x)$	Wind speed at x downstream
$u_i(x)$	Wind speed at x downstream behind rotor i
u_i^{inc}	Incoming wind speed to rotor i
(u, v, w)	Wind speed components
u_*	Friction velocity
(x, y, z)	Cartesian coordinate system
z_0	Aerodynamic roughness length

Greek symbols

α	Map rotation
α_c	Charnock parameter
δ	Kronecker delta
ϵ	Viscous dissipation
ε_{ijk}	Levi-Civita symbol
η	Wind farm efficiency unless otherwise stated
η_{SF}	Wind farm efficiency w. respect to Shell Flats
θ	Potential temperature
θ_v	Virtual potential temperature
κ	Von kármán constant
ρ	Density, correlation coefficient
$\rho_{x,y}$	Correlation coefficient
σ	Length scale (wake expansion), standard deviation
σ_0	Length scale (near-wake expansion)
σ_e	Effective length scale (wake expansion)
ϕ	WRF variable or Latitude when stated
φ	Wind direction
ψ	Constant
ω	Angular velocity of Earth
Δ	Difference
Ψ_M	Atmospheric stability function
Ω	Earth rotation vector

General subscripts

Earth	Variable relative to Earth
ijk	Variable in cell ijk
z	Variable at z level

Specific subscript for P

Gross	Gross power
Net	Net power
SF	Estimated power at Shell Flats
t	Power from one turbine

Specific subscripts for u

0	Absolute wind speed at hub height
∞	Free stream wind speed
d	Velocity deficit profile
M	Wind speed magnitude
r_0	Wind speed behind rotor
s	Maximum velocity deficit
$(XX)m(Location)$	Wind speed at XX meter at $Location$ on meteorological mast

Superscripts

$\overline{(\dots)}$	Mean component
$(\dots)'$	Fluctuating component

Mathematical notation

Einstein notation is used in this report for the governing equations. This implies that

$$u_i = [u, v, w],$$
$$x_i = [x, y, z]$$

and

$$\frac{\partial(\dots)}{\partial x_i} = \left[\frac{\partial(\dots)}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial(\dots)}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial(\dots)}{\partial z} \right]$$

If the same index appears twice in the same term, a summation is implied as

$$u_i u_i = uu + vv + ww$$

or

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z}$$

for partial derivatives.

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

In this chapter, the motivation for studying wind farm wakes is presented along with a short account of wind turbine wake physics and models. The existing research of wakes in within and after wind farms will be reviewed. For analysing wind farm wakes, a site is chosen to investigate which is introduced in this chapter. Lastly, the scope of work and specifications for this project is presented.

1.1 Motivation

Offshore wind energy still continues to grow since the first offshore wind farm Vindeby was installed in 1991. Since 2011 alone, the offshore wind capacity has increased with 460% as of 2017. Most of the installed wind energy can be found in Europe, mainly in the English and German seas (Global Wind Energy Council, 2018a). There is no indication that this trend will not continue with predictions of the offshore wind energy increasing development, not only in European markets but also in Asia and USA (Global Wind Energy Council, 2018b). The prediction is encouraged by the European Commission with their climate strategies for 2050 including that 20% of the European energy ought to be from renewable sources in 2020 and by 2030 this number should at least be 27%, (European Commission, 2018).

With the increasing amount of installed wind energy, the need for placing wind farms closer together arises. This introduces the problem of wind farms affecting each other with their wake. For existing wind farms, the consequence is a lower energy production and for the wind farm developer it can further complicate the wind resources assessment of an area. It can be assumed that the wind resources will be less in close proximity to another wind farm, but how much and to what extend?

Wind farm wakes have been investigated via satellite images, where it previously has been found that the wake recovered to 2% of the free stream velocity 5-20 km downstream of the wind farm depending on the atmospheric stability (Christensen and Hasager, 2005). Later, satellite images revealed wind farm wakes stretching as far as 75 km downstream (Hasager et al., 2015). Recently, another method were taken in use for the first time to observe wakes: a research aircraft which performed measurements over wind farms in the North Sea. From these images, wind farm wakes up to 70 km were observed (Platis et al., 2018). The mentioned observations all emphasise the need for further study of these, in some cases, far extending wakes.

This project will focus on how the wind farm wakes affect the wind resources.

1.2 Introduction to Wakes

A wind turbine extracts momentum from the atmospheric flow and converts it into electricity. Behind the turbine, the momentum decreases and there is a reduced wind speed and an increased turbulence. The reduced wind speed and increased turbulence can lead to a lower production and higher loads when there is another turbine downstream.

The flow right behind the turbine is referred to as the near wake and extends approximately 1-5 rotor diameters downstream, (Murcia Leon, 2017). The flow is dependent on the blade aerodynamics and within this range, tip vortices can occur. With the flow within the wake being slower than outside the wake, a wake shear layer develops where the flow outside the wake mixes with the flow within the wake. Further downstream, the flow will only be governed by turbulence mixing and is referred to as the far wake. If the wake continues downstream undisturbed it will return to the free stream conditions. The wind speed deficit profile can approximately be described with a Gaussian distribution in the far wake.

For wakes in a wind farm, the process becomes more complex. The wakes from the individual turbines can interact with each other or meandering can alter the wake direction. The complexity of wakes within a wind farm was witnessed over Horns Rev 1 offshore wind farm in 2008, see Figure 1.1, where the turbine wakes were revealed due to special atmospheric conditions.

Figure 1.1: Wind farm wake captured 12th February 2008 over Horns Rev 1 offshore wind farm, (Hasager et al., 2013). The wind farm is not in operation.

1.3 Wake Models

When analysing wakes, models have long been used in an attempt to describe these. The models range in complexity and computational time but overall one can talk of three model categories:

- Engineering.
- Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD).
- Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP).

The engineering models are analytical or semi-analytical models. A limited number of variables can be altered to change the expansion of the wake downstream and the wake is often simplified in geometry. An example is the Jensen model by Jensen (1983) where one variable defines the wake expansion and the wind speed deficit profile is simplified to a to-hat profile. This model will be reviewed in more detail in Chapter 3. CFD models range in complexity between them, from linearised Navier-Stokes equation, which is implemented in the software FUGA (DTU Wind Energy, 2018), Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) to LES. The Weather Research & Forecasting model (WRF) is a well known NWP model.

The engineering models are typically faster than CFD or NWP, but less information regarding the flow will be obtained whereas with an LES simulation, a lot of information will be gained but it will cost more computationally wise. Depending on the field of interest and scales that are to be investigated, the different models can be utilised. It is preferable to use LES when resolving smaller turbulent scales, in the order of 1-1000 m, whereas the Jensen model can be sufficient to estimate wake losses from one turbine to another.

WRF works on the mesoscale level ($\approx 10^3 - 10^6$ metres, (Stull, 1988)) and is in particular suitable to use for estimating wind resources in an area. The model is restricted to only resolve scales down to approximately 10^3 meters. Since wind turbines affect the flow on smaller scales, a parametrisation is needed to account for the presence of these. In WRF, this has been implemented in different ways.

The wind turbines can be modelled as an increased roughness in those cells they are present as in (Barrie and Kirk-Davidoff, 2010). In 2012, a parametrisation was introduced by Fitch et al. (2012) which imposes a momentum sink on the mean flow and adds turbulent kinetic energy as the remaining kinetic energy that is not transformed into electricity. A few years later, Volker et al. (2015) introduced the Explicit Wake Parametrisation (EWP) where the turbulent kinetic energy due to wind turbines is a result of the wind shear. WRF and the wind farm parametrisation EWP will be reviewed in greater detail in Chapter 3.

Besides using the numerical models, various measurements can be obtained to analyse wake effects, for instance meteorological masts, LiDAR, sonar, satellite images or Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) from wind turbines.

1.4 Literature Review

The three types of models have been used throughout the years, both compared with each other and validated against in situ data. There are still studies on how to best calibrate the engineering models where they have been compared to more advanced models as by (Andersen et al., 2014).

The two wind farm parametrisations in WRF, Fitch and EWP, have been compared with each other and utilised individually. Validation on the Fitch parametrisation was performed by (Lee and Lundquist, 2017) over a heavily packed area with wind turbines. The investigation showed that using the wind farm parametrisation improved the power production estimation and that it was dependent on vertical resolution. (Volker et al., 2015) validated the EWP parametrisation by comparing it with SCADA data from Horns Rev I Offshore Wind Farm and meteorological masts to the east of Horns Rev I. Results were also obtained using the Fitch parametrisation. Both models yielded approximately equally long wakes but Fitch has a faster return to the free stream velocity. Recently, the Fitch parametrisation has been validated against the individual aircraft observations presented in (Platis et al., 2018) by (Siedersleben et al., 2018). They found that the Fitch parametrisation simulated the spatial extend of the wake well but underestimated the wind speed deficit within the wake. The incoming wind speed to the wind farms was also underestimated.

Besides being used for wake effects, both parametrisations have been used to evaluate the wind turbines' impact on the mesoscale climate in (Pryor et al., 2018a,b). From both parametrisations, the impact on local to mesoscale climate was deemed small. The Fitch parametrisation yielded a larger change in both wind speed, near-surface temperature and specific humidity compared to EWP.

For wakes from wind turbines, most research so far has been concerning wake effects *within* a wind farm. The wind farm efficiency is often used to evaluate the wake losses as has been done by (Barthelmie et al., 2007) on Middelgrunden and later on Horns Rev and Nysted with respect to wind turbine spacing, wind speed, turbulence intensity and atmospheric stability, (Barthelmie et al., 2013). SCADA data from various wind farms have been used to validate models. (Nygaard, 2014) compared the Jensen model to SCADA from three large offshore wind farms. The Jensen model was applied to a row of turbines and for all wind farms the predictions compared well with the observations. For one of the wind farms the wake loss was underestimated but (Nygaard, 2014) concluded it can be due to difference in inflow conditions and not necessarily due to the wake model.

(Barthelmie et al., 2009) used SCADA data from Horns Rev to evaluate 6 different flow models (engineering and CFD). It was seen that CFD tends to underestimate the power production but it was also concluded that more data was needed to validate either of the models properly.

Similarly, (Moriarty et al., 2014) validated different wake models (engineering, RANS and LES) along a row of turbines in Horns Rev and Lillgrund. They found it difficult to conclude whether one model performed better than another as there were no obvious trends between the accuracy of the models. It was also noted by (Moriarty et al., 2014) that more observations under different operating and atmospheric conditions could improve the validation.

WRF with the Fitch parametrisation was used to evaluate wake losses along a row of turbines in Horns Rev by (Jiménez et al., 2015), where SCADA was available for comparison. The power deficit along the row was determined with respect to different wind directions, atmospheric stability

and turbulence intensity. They found that using the turbine manufacturers data for power curve and thrust coefficient rather than using default values from WRF and the parametrisations, further improved the estimate of the power deficit. The wind farm wake was briefly evaluated.

(Volker et al., 2017) used both the EWP and Fitch parametrisation in WRF to evaluate fictive wind farms of different scales and the internal wake effects. The wind farm efficiency was evaluated with respect to three different wind climates, four wind farm layouts and three turbine spacings. A small wind farm with narrow wind turbine spacing proved as efficient as a large wind farm with wide turbine spacing in some wind climates.

The wake effects *after* a wind farm, or the effect of neighbouring wind farms, have not been investigated in the same degree as wake effects within one. (Nygaard, 2014) assessed the wake losses of Nysted after the construction of Rødsand II by using wind farm data (SCADA) data which only were available for Nysted at the time. Data from Nysted showed a decrease in wind farm efficiency and increase in turbulence intensity if the wind came through Rødsand II first. The case was investigated later again (Nygaard and Hansen, 2016), where data from both Rødsand II and Nysted were available. The Jensen model was applied along a row of turbines from Rødsand II to Nysted. The investigation showed that the additional wake losses experienced by Nysted from Rødsand II was limited to the first turbines in the row. Longer down the row, the turbine power production converged towards the same power production as before Rødsand II.

Rødsand II and Nysted is also used as a case for the work of (van der Laan et al., 2015) where a RANS model is used to investigate the impact of the Coriolis force. Results of the investigation indicated that if examining wind farm clusters, the Coriolis force should be included in a RANS model.

An extensive research on different models were made in connection with the EERA-DTOC (European Energy Research Alliance - Design Tools for Offshore wind farm clusters) project, (Hansen et al., 2015). Different models were used to evaluate the wake losses for Rødsand II caused by Nysted. The Jensen model was used along with FUGA and SCADA data. Various CFD models were also utilised. As a mesoscale model, WRF was used with EWP. All the models captured the overall trend with respect to where the largest wind speed deficit was expected to occur in Rødsand II. Unfortunately, the results using WRF with EWP were not shown in the paper. None of the models, including WRF, was able to predict the wind farm efficiency of Rødsand II with respect to the wind direction. The models all agreed on from which wind direction the wind farm efficiency was lowest but overestimated it by approximately 5-15 percentage points.

Recently, an extensive study were made regarding wind farm wakes, not only with respect to the physics but also regarding economy and law by (Lundquist et al., 2018). The research focused on three wind farms in Texas where one is placed directly in front of the other in the prevailing wind direction. The results showed a decrease in power production but which mostly occurred during night. Besides the WRF simulations used for the research, they were restricted to using public available data.

In a lot of studies, models have been validated against in situ data such as meteorological masts or wind farm data (SCADA). There are, however, uncertainties when it comes to these. (Barthelmie et al., 2009) addressed these shortly mentioning the uncertainties in establishing a free stream flow, estimating the wind direction from either meteorological masts or wind farm data, accuracy of site specific power curve and thrust coefficient and other variables. The uncertainty of the wind direction alone was addressed in (Gaumont et al., 2014). It was accounted by (Murcia Leon, 2017;

Barthelmie et al., 2009) that when using SCADA for validation, proper post processing is necessary to identify valid data. How to handle the uncertainties relates to the objective of the study and how it limits the measurement sources.

1.5 Site to Investigate: The Irish Sea

In this project, wind farm wakes will be investigated for a cluster of wind farms in the Irish Sea near the British Coast. Close to one another lies the wind farms: Barrow Offshore Wind Farm (BOW), Ormonde Offshore Wind Farm (OOWF), Walney Phase 1 (WOW01), Walney Phase 2 (WOW02), Walney Phase 3 (WOW03), Walney Phase 4 (WOW04) and West of Duddon Sands (WDS), see Figure 1.2. The wind farms are in close proximity to each other with approximately 3 km between West of Duddon Sands and Barrow and 11 km between Ormonde and Barrow. In Figure 1.2, two meteorological masts to the west of Blackpool are also plotted. They are Shell Flats, one being 50 meters tall (SF50m) and the other 80 meters (SF80m). A larger version of the two maps can be found in Appendix A.

Up until 2011, Barrow was the only wind farm in the area. In 2011 and 2012, Walney Phase 1 and 2 and Ormonde were commissioned. West of Duddon Sands was commissioned in 2014 and is located to the west of Barrow. Walney Extension (WOW03 and WOW04) was commissioned in September 2018 and is an extension to the existing Walney 1 and Walney 2, (Ørsted, 2018). The wind farms Barrow, West of Duddon Sands and Walney Phase 1 through 4 are all owned by Ørsted while Ormonde is owned by Vattenfall and AMF, (Vattenfall, 2015). The wind farm specifications are listed in Table 1.1.

With all the wind farms being in approximately 54° , the prevailing wind is expected to be from the west. Hence, it can be expected that power production from Barrow has decreased since West of Duddon Sands has been operational.

Wind farm data (SCADA) is provided by Ørsted for the wind farms they own, i.e. BOW, WDS, WOW01, WOW02, WOW03 and WOW04.

Figure 1.2: Location and layout of the six wind farms in the Irish Sea.

	Commissioned	No. of turbines	Turbine type	Diameter [m]	Hub height [m aMSL]	Farm capacity [MW]
BOW	2006	30	V90-3.0MW	90	75	90
WOW01	2011	51	SWT-3.6-107	107	83.5	183.6
WOW02	2012	51	SWT-3.6-120	120	90.15	183.6
OOWF	2012	30	5M (EON)	126	90	150
WDS	2014	108	SWT-3.6-120	120	90	389
WOW03	2018	40	V164-8.0MW*	164	105	330
WOW04	2018	47	SWT-7.0-154	154	105	329

Table 1.1: Wind farm specifications. All information obtained from www.4coffshore.com. (*) V164-8.0MW is power boosted to 8.25 MW.

1.6 Scope of Work

When building a new wind farm, the annual energy production (AEP) must be estimated to evaluate the expected income for a future wind farm. The resulting AEP is a product of a wind resource model and the wake model used for the wind farm layout as illustrated in Figure 1.3. This project will focus on how the *wind resources* are modelled and, specifically, if there is anything to gain from utilising a wind farm parametrisation. The wind resource assessment will be made with WRF (3.8.1) and wind farms will be modelled using the EWP parametrisation as *real* simulations, i.e. the simulations evolve in time as function of evolving weather conditions. When making a wind resource assessment, it is necessary to simulate for at least one year to avoid seasonal bias and it is the long-term average that is of interest rather than specific cases. For this project it therefore does not matter whether WRF estimates the wind resources correctly for each successive time step but rather how the distribution is during one year.

The wind farm parametrisation is of main interest in this project. A case study is chosen where wind farm wakes are expected to have an impact which is why the Irish Sea is chosen, as there are only 3 km between two of the wind farms. Having in mind that wind farm wakes between 5-75 km has been observed (Christensen and Hasager, 2005; Hasager et al., 2015; Platis et al., 2018), it can be assumed that wind farm wakes have an impact on this specific site.

The project will evaluate the wind resources where Barrow offshore wind farm is located and how it is affected by the upstream wind farms. Walney extension will not be included in the study as it has just recently been commissioned. When referring to the *upstream wind farms* in the remainder

Figure 1.3: Input for estimating AEP, (Murcia Leon, 2017).

of the project, it will only include Ormonde, West of Dudon Sands, Walney 1 and Walney 2. These wind farms will not always be upstream with respect to Barrow, but as the prevailing wind is from west, they will be upstream for the most part.

As wind farm data is available for Barrow, the wind resources, including the EWP parametrisation, can be validated with these.

The project will have below objectives in order to validate the wind resources, including the (EWP) wind farm parametrisation, for Barrow:

- Verify wind climatology in the Irish Sea obtained from WRF.
- Assess wake effects on the downstream wind farm, Barrow (BOW), from SCADA data.
- Assess necessary WRF resolution using both EWP and Fitch parametrisation.
- Validate wind resources and EWP with SCADA data.

Both EWP and the Fitch parametrisation have been evaluated within one wind farm by (Lee and Lundquist, 2017; Volker et al., 2015; Siedersleben et al., 2018), but the wind farm wake has not yet been validated. Volker et al. (2015) did consider the wind farm wake in his work but is firstly, limited in spatial resolution to the two meteorological masts that are to the east of Horns Rev and secondly, only simulates a limited number of idealised cases. Siedersleben et al. (2018) validated the Fitch parametrisation as real runs against observations from an aircraft presented by (Platis et al., 2018) but only for specific cases, i.e. instantaneous wake conditions.

This study varies from both of these. Firstly, since only *real* simulations are used and secondly, as the study focuses on wind resources assessment and not specific cases. The validation will be performed for the EWP parametrisation.

The provided data for the project is introduced in Chapter 2. In Chapter 3, the method and relevant governing equations for atmospheric flow is presented. It is also in this chapter the set up of the WRF model is presented, including physics, model grids and post processing. Following is Chapter 4, which covers the quality control of the data and presents the criteria for the comparison of different data sources. In Chapter 5, the results are presented. The conclusion and any remarks regarding future works is in Chapter 6.

CHAPTER 2

Data

For analysing the wind farms in the Irish Sea, several different data sources are utilised. This chapter will present the data that have been provided or obtained elsewhere. Wind farm data (SCADA) have been provided by the wind farm owner. Two data set from meteorological masts in the Irish Sea have been obtained, where the first is from ([Marine Data Exchange, 2018](#)) and the second from the wind farm owner. Data from the New European Wind Atlas have been provided by DTU Wind Energy.

2.1 SCADA

SCADA data have been provided by Ørsted for the four wind farms: Barrow (BOW), Walney Phase 1 (WOW01), Walney Phase 2 (WOW02) and West of Duddon Sands (WDS). The wind farm Ormonde (OOWF) is also in the area, but since it is not owned by Ørsted, data are not available for the wind farm. The provided data from Ørsted have gone through post processing which, amongst other things, ensures that the data are in the same format even though the data comes from different manufacturers, i.e. Vestas or Siemens.

The data consists of 10-minute averages and includes a mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum value for each input signal. There are measurements for power production, several different inputs for wind speed (from nacelle anemometers, estimated from power curve etc.) and various relevant information such as location of each turbine, power curve and thrust coefficient (P and C_T). In Table 2.1, the start and end date for the SCADA data are listed for the wind farms.

As Ørsted does not own Ormonde (OOWF), they cannot provide the power curve for the turbines in the farm. The power curve is instead of provided by DTU Wind Energy from a wind turbine catalogue. The power curve and thrust coefficient are shown in Figure 2.1.

	BOW	WOW01	WOW02	WDS
SCADA start date [dd-mm-yyyy]	04-03-2006	20-10-2010	01-11-2011	16-01-2014
SCADA end date [dd-mm-yyyy]	15-08-2018	27-07-2017	27-07-2017	27-07-2017

Table 2.1: SCADA data availability.

Of available measurements and variables, a few are highlighted below as they are particular useful for the analysis.

Filter

There are several measurements which indicate whether a turbine is available and producing power for a complete 10-minute period. Ørsted has combined several of these criteria into one variable named Filter, consisting of logical true or false for each time step for each turbine. If a turbine is available for all 10 minutes, has a minimum power production larger than 0 and is not curtailed, the turbine is assigned a logical true. If a turbine does not fulfil all of the requirements, a logical false is assigned.

Median wind direction

A median wind direction for the wind farm is computed by Ørsted. The wind direction is calibrated by analysing selected turbine pairs and making sure the power deficit between them is aligned with the directions of expected highest wake loss. As the turbine yaw can have a bias from the actual wind direction which is not necessarily constant in time, the yaw analysis is continuously updated throughout the period for computing the median wind direction.

Free standing turbines

Based on wind farm layout and a simple wake model, the free standing turbines, i.e. not waked turbines, within the wind farm itself is estimated. For each turbine, a wider wake than what would be considered normally is computed. This gives the 'worst-case-wake-scenario' for the wind farm and tells which turbines are not in the internal wakes.

Figure 2.1: Power curve for turbines in (a) V90-3.0MW (BOW), (b) SWT-3.6-107 (WOW01), (c) SWT-3.6-120 (WOW02 and WDS) and (d) 5M (OOWF).

2.2 Shell Flats

Data from the two meteorological masts Shell Flats will be used to investigate whether WRF can model the climatology in the Irish Sea. The two Shell Flats met masts are situated outside the coast with Blackpool to the east, the case study wind farms approximately 25 km to the north and Ireland approximately 200 km to the west. The location can be seen in on the map in [Figure 1.2](#) or [Appendix A](#). The one mast is 50 meters high and the other is 80 meters.

The Irish Sea is influenced by the tide. If looking up a tide table, ([BBC weather, 2018](#)), for the nearby city Blackpool, it can be seen that the sea level can vary 5-8 meters during a day. This change in sea level means that the instrument altitude might vary with ± 4 meters during one day. In this project, there will not be performed any corrections for the tide level.

Measurement campaign: 2011-2012

The data, along with a report on the measurement campaign, are obtained from ([Marine Data Exchange, 2018](#)). The campaign covers July 2011 to August 2012. Data from both masts are available, however not from all instruments for the 50-meter mast. Therefore, only the 80-meter mast is used for analysis. The 80-meter mast has two booms, one towards north-west (NW) and the other towards south-east (SE). The instrumentation of the mast is listed in [Table 2.2](#), where location of the instruments is indicated in parentheses. When mentioning Shell Flats onwards, data from the 80 meter mast are implied.

Measurement	Instrument	Height [m]
Pressure	Setra 278	Platform height
Relative humidity	HMP45AC	Platform height, 82 (top)
Temperature	Vaisala	Platform height, 82 (top)
Wind direction	Wind vane: Vector W200P	78 (NW, SE)
	Ultrasonic anemometer: WS425 A1E2A	80 (NW)
Wind speed	Cup anemometer: Vector A100L2	50 (NW, SE), 70 (NW, SE), 80 (SE), 82 (top)
	Ultrasonic anemometer: WS425 A1E2A	80 (NW)

Table 2.2: Instrumentation of Shell Flats 80m mast from ([Dong Energy / ScottishPower, 2011](#)).

Measurement campaign: 2014-2015

Data from Shell Flats from October 2014 to November 2015 are provided by Ørsted for the wind farm wake analysis. Only the 80 meter mast is used as to have the same reference mast for the two periods. Between 2012 and 2015, the ultra sonic anemometer on the north-west boom at 80 meters is decommissioned. In July 2015, it is replaced with a cup anemometer. The instrumentation for the mast can be seen in Table 2.3.

Measurement	Instrument	Height [m]
Pressure	Setra 278	Platform height
Relative humidity	HMP45AC	Platform height, 82 (top)
Temperature	Vaisala	Platform height, 82 (top)
Wind direction	Wind vane: Vector W200P	78 (NW, SE)
Wind speed	Cup anemometer: Vector A100L2	50 (NW,SE), 70 (NW,SE), 80 (NW,SE), 82 (top)

Table 2.3: Instrumentation of Shell Flats 80m mast from Ørsted.

2.3 WRF: New European Wind Atlas

For the purpose of verifying that WRF can indeed estimate the climatology in the Irish Sea, data from the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) have been provided by DTU Wind Energy at the location of the Shell Flats met mast. The data covers from January 2011 through December 2012. The grid spacing for the New European Wind Atlas is 3×3 km. The variables are listed in Table 2.4. The data has gone through post processing by DTU Wind Energy.

Variable	Unit	Levels [m]
Friction velocity	[m/s]	0
Inverse Obukhov length	[m ⁻¹]	0
Wind speed	[m/s]	50, 75, 100, 150, 200, 250 and 500
Wind direction	[°]	50, 75, 100, 150, 200, 250 and 500
Air temperature	[K]	2, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200, 250 and 500
Surface temperature	[K]	2
Surface pressure	[Pa]	2
Specific humidity	[-]	2

Table 2.4: NEWA data at Shell Flats location.

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Method & Model Set Up

This chapter will start with introducing some basic statistics. Afterwards, the Jensen wake model and PARK2 will be presented. PARK2 is based on the Jensen model and implemented in the software Wind Atlas and Analysis and Application Program (WAsP) developed by DTU Wind Energy, which will be used in the study. Afterwards, the governing equations for the Explicit Wake Parametrisation (EWP) will be presented followed by the basic equations for atmospheric stability and boundary layer profile. A method for estimating the wind farm efficiency for Barrow will be presented before the WRF set up is reviewed. This includes an account of the simulations to be performed and model specifications for the physics and model grids. In the end, there is a brief review on how WRF outputs are post processed.

3.1 Basic Statistics

Some basic statistical methods will be used throughout, mainly in connection with data quality control. When having one time series, x , the mean and variance are defined as

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i, \quad (3.1)$$

$$\sigma_x^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2, \quad (3.2)$$

respectively with N being the number of samples in the time series. The standard deviation σ_x , can be determined from the variance, σ_x^2 . When comparing two time series, x and y , one can use the correlation coefficient, $\rho_{x,y}$:

$$\rho_{x,y} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} = \frac{\sigma_{x,y}^2}{\sigma_x \sigma_y} \quad (3.3)$$

where $\sigma_{x,y}^2$ is the covariance and σ_x and σ_y is the standard deviation of time series x and y , respectively. It applies that $-1 \leq \rho_{x,y} \leq 1$ where the two extremes are if x and y are reverse or directly correlated.

For the different data sets, it can be necessary to compare the measurements of wind direction between two instruments. The difference between two wind directions is computed as

$$\Delta(\varphi_2, \varphi_1) = 2 \tan^{-1} (\tan(0.5[\varphi_2 - \varphi_1])) \quad (3.4)$$

from (Farrugia et al., 2009) where φ_1 and φ_2 are two wind directions measured by the two respective instruments.

The mean wind direction from a time series, cannot be computed from Equation (3.1). First, the horizontal components of the wind, u and v , is determined from the wind speed magnitude, u_M , as

$$u = -|u_M| \sin(\varphi), \quad v = -|u_M| \cos(\varphi). \quad (3.5)$$

Equation (3.1) is used to determine the mean of the two horizontal components, \bar{u} and \bar{v} . The mean wind direction is obtained as

$$\bar{\varphi} = \arctan \left(\frac{\bar{u}}{\bar{v}} \right) + \psi \quad (3.6)$$

where the constant ψ is

$$\psi = \begin{cases} 180 & \text{for } \arctan(\bar{u}/\bar{v}) < 180 \\ -180 & \text{for } \arctan(\bar{u}/\bar{v}) > 180 \end{cases} \quad (3.7)$$

Most software today, such as MATLAB and Python, has a function named `atan2` to determine $\arctan(\dots)$, which expands the interval to $[-180^\circ, 180^\circ]$. When using `atan2`, $\psi = 180$ always.

3.2 Jensen Wake Model

The Jensen wake model will be used to describe the wake behind a turbine. This specific model will be described as it is also the basis for the wake effect model, PARK2, in the DTU software Wind Atlas and Analysis and Application Program (WASP, v12). The following is based on the work of (Jensen, 1983) and (Rathmann et al., 2018). The notation has been altered slightly for this project.

The Jensen model assumes a linear expansion of the wake behind a turbine which can be seen in Figure 3.1. It is assumed that the wind speed deficit is a simple top-hat profile. The inflow wind speed, u_∞ , is a uniform wind. When passing through the turbine rotor, the wind speed right behind the rotor decreases to u_{r_0} which at a distance x downstream results in the wind speed $u(x)$. Right after the turbine, the wake will have a diameter of r_0 , equal to the rotor diameter, and at the distance x , the wake diameter will have increased to r . As the wake is assumed to expand linearly, the wake radius as a function of the downstream distance can be expressed as

$$r = kx + r_0 \quad (3.8)$$

where k is the wake decay constant. The momentum balance from the turbine and to x downstream is

$$\pi r_0^2 u_{r_0} + \pi (r^2 - r_0^2) u_\infty = \pi r^2 u(x) \quad (3.9)$$

If assuming that $u_{r_0} = \frac{1}{3}u_\infty$ and inserting the expression for r , the momentum balance results in

$$u(x) = u_\infty \left[1 - \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{r_0}{r_0 + kx} \right)^2 \right] = u_\infty \left[1 - 2a \left(\frac{r_0}{r_0 + kx} \right)^2 \right] \quad (3.10)$$

where the last equality comes from recognising that the axial induction factor, $a = 1/3$, for an optimum rotor. The wind speed deficit is

$$\Delta u(x) = u_\infty - u(x) = u_\infty 2a \left(\frac{r_0}{r_0 + kx} \right)^2 \quad (3.11)$$

Figure 3.1: Wake behind a single rotor from (Jensen, 1983, fig. 1).

3.2.1 PARK2

The PARK2 model, which is implemented in the wake effect model in WAsP, is based on the Jensen model, Equation (3.11). From optimum rotor theory it applies that $2a = 1 - \sqrt{1 - C_T}$ with C_T being the thrust coefficient. The wind speed behind rotor i is defined as

$$\Delta u_i(x) = u_i^{inc} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - C_T(u_i^{inc})} \right) \left(\frac{D_i}{D_i + 2k(x - x_i)} \right)^2 \quad (3.12)$$

with u_i^{inc} being the incoming wind speed to rotor i and the thrust coefficient being a function of this wind speed. For PARK2, the rotor and wake radius is replaced with rotor diameter. At x , the wind speed deficit is evaluated which is at the distance $x - x_i$ downstream from turbine i placed in x_i . If there should be overlapping wakes, PARK2 determines the incoming wind speed to rotor i with linear superposition as

$$u_j^{inc} = u_\infty - \sum_i^{N_t} \Delta u_i(x) \frac{A_{ij}^{overlap}}{A_{ij}^{rotor}} \quad (3.13)$$

where u_∞ is the initial free-stream wind speed, N_t , is the number of upwind turbines, A_{ij}^{rotor} is the rotor area and $A_{ij}^{overlap}$ is the overlapping area between the rotor and the wake hitting it.

The wake decay coefficient, k , should be chosen with care as it will determine how wide or narrow the wake is. The recommendations from DTU Wind Energy is to choose $k_{onshore} = 0.09$ and $k_{offshore} = 0.06$, (Rathmann et al., 2018). It should be noted that these values are calibrated for the PARK2 model, and the same values for k will not necessarily yield the same results if used in the Jensen model.

3.3 WRF & The Explicit Wake Parametrisation

Before introducing some of the governing equations, it is important to note that the Weather Research and Forecasting Model (WRF) is a very extensive model which includes a wide range of physics and several options for each. This section will focus on the wind farm parametrisation and the relevant governing equations. The reader is referred to (Skamarock et al., 2018) if wanting to know more about WRF and the remaining governing equations implemented in the software.

The equations related to the Explicit Wake Parametrisation (EWP) is from (Volker et al., 2015) where details of the derivations can be found. The derivations will not be reviewed in details in this section.

3.3.1 Equation of Motion

The flow is governed by the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations which in (Volker et al., 2015) is stated as

$$\underbrace{\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial t}}_{\text{I}} + \underbrace{\bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j}}_{\text{II}} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial \overline{u'_i u'_j}}{\partial x_j}}_{\text{III}} = - \underbrace{\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i}}_{\text{IV}} - \underbrace{2\varepsilon_{ijk} \Omega_j \bar{u}_k}_{\text{V}} - \underbrace{\delta_{i3} g}_{\text{VI}} + \underbrace{\bar{f}_{d_i}}_{\text{VII}} \quad (3.14)$$

where

- Term I is the storage of momentum.
- Term II is the advection of the mean momentum due to the mean wind speed \bar{u}_j .
- Term III is the influence of Reynolds' stress, $\overline{u'_i u'_j}$, on the mean flow.
- Term IV is the forces from the mean pressure-gradient.
- Term V is the Coriolis force with Ω_j being the Earth's rotational vector.
- Term VI is the gravitational acceleration (only in the vertical direction).
- Term VII is an ensemble-averaged *horizontal* force due to wind turbines ($\bar{f}_{d_3} = 0$).

In Equation (3.14), an overbar $\overline{(\dots)}$ indicates an ensemble average and $(\dots)'$ a fluctuating part. u is the wind speed, ρ the density of air, p the pressure and g the gravitational acceleration. The Earth's rotation vector is defined as $\Omega = \{0, \omega \cos(\phi), \omega \sin(\phi)\}$ where $\omega = 7.27 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is the angular velocity of the Earth and ϕ is latitude, (Stull, 1988). ε_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol and δ_{ij} is Kroneckers delta. The term \bar{f}_{d_i} is introduced for the EWP scheme and represents the force due to the wind turbine.

The velocity deficit profile, u_d , behind a turbine rotor is

$$\bar{u}_d = \bar{u}_s \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z-h}{\sigma} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{y}{\sigma} \right)^2 \right] \quad (3.15)$$

where u_s is the maximum velocity deficit at the centre of the wake, h is the hub height and σ is a length scale that governs the wake expansion defined as

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{2K}{\bar{u}_0} x + \sigma_0^2 \quad (3.16)$$

The wind speed u_0 is the absolute wind speed at hub height and $K(x, y, t) = K_m(x, y, h, t)$ is the turbulence diffusion coefficient which is determined from the planetary boundary layer (PBL)

scheme in WRF. The initial length scale σ_0 is not known and needs to be chosen. σ_0 accounts for the near-wake expansion whereas σ describes the far wake. In (Volker et al., 2015), σ_0 is chosen based on an investigation of Horns Rev.

The velocity deficit profile can also be stated in term of a thrust coefficient, C_T , as

$$\bar{u}_d = \frac{C_T r_0^2 \bar{u}_0}{4\sigma^2} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z-h}{\sigma} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{y}{h} \right)^2 \right] \quad (3.17)$$

The grid cell averaged force due to a turbine is defined as

$$\langle \bar{f}_{d_1}(k) \rangle = -\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{8}} \frac{C_T r_0^2 \bar{u}_0^2}{\Delta x \Delta y \sigma_e} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z-h}{\sigma_e} \right)^2 \right] \cos[\varphi(k)] \quad (3.18)$$

$$\langle \bar{f}_{d_2}(k) \rangle = -\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{8}} \frac{C_T r_0^2 \bar{u}_0^2}{\Delta x \Delta y \sigma_e} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z-h}{\sigma_e} \right)^2 \right] \sin[\varphi(k)] \quad (3.19)$$

in the x and y direction respectively with Δx and Δy being the respective grid spacing. In the vertical direction, $\bar{f}_{d_3} = 0$. The height $z = z(k)$ is the height at the centre of a layer k . $\varphi(k)$ is the wind direction. The length scale σ has been replaced with the effective length scale σ_e defined as

$$\sigma_e = \frac{1}{\ell} = \int_0^\ell \sigma dx = \frac{\bar{u}_0}{3K\ell} \left[\left(\frac{2K}{\bar{u}_0} \ell + \sigma_0^2 \right)^{3/2} - \sigma_0^3 \right] \quad (3.20)$$

The effective length scale is related to the model grid size where ℓ is the length downstream that the wake has travelled within a grid cell.

3.3.2 Turbulent Kinetic Energy

The equation for the mean turbulent kinetic energy, \bar{e} , is

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc} \frac{\partial \bar{e}}{\partial t} + \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{e}}{\partial x_j} = \delta_{i3} \frac{g}{\bar{\theta}_v} \left(\overline{u'_i \theta'_v} \right) - \overline{u'_i u'_j} \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial (\overline{u'_j e})}{\partial x_j} - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial (\overline{u'_i p'})}{\partial x_i} - \epsilon & & & & & & & \\ \text{I} & \text{II} & \text{III} & \text{IV} & \text{V} & \text{VI} & \text{VII} & \end{array} \quad (3.21)$$

where

- Term I is the storage of turbulent kinetic energy, TKE.
- Term II is the advection of TKE due to the mean wind speed \bar{u}_j .
- Term III is the buoyant production.
- Term IV is the contribution to TKE from shear production.
- Term V is the turbulent transport of TKE.
- Term VI is the pressure correlation term.
- Term VII is the viscous dissipation of TKE.

where the same notation as in Equation (3.14) applies to (3.21) and where $\bar{\theta}_v$ is the virtual potential temperature in Kelvin. The term $\overline{u'_i \theta'_v}$ is a heat flux.

In (Volker et al., 2015), the TKE is stated in the compact form:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{e}}{\partial t} + \bar{T} = \bar{p}_s + \bar{p}_b + \bar{p}_t - \epsilon \quad (3.22)$$

where \bar{T} is the transport of TKE covering Term II, V and VI in Equation (3.21), \bar{p}_s covers shear production (Term IV), \bar{p}_b covers the buoyant production (Term III) and \bar{p}_t is the turbulence induced by the turbine rotor which is introduced for the EWP.

For the mesoscale model, the volume averaged values are computed. The volume averaged turbulence induced by a turbine, $\langle \bar{p}_t \rangle$, is defined as

$$\langle \bar{p}_t \rangle \approx -\rho A_r C_T \langle \overline{u_{i,h} u'_{i,h}{}^2} \rangle \quad (3.23)$$

where A_r is the area of the rotor, C_T the thrust coefficient and $u_{i,h}$ is the wind speed at hub height h . As $\langle \bar{p}_t \rangle < 0$, the turbine rotor introduces a TKE sink. In the EWP, $\langle \bar{p}_t \rangle$ is deemed small, hence neglected in the TKE budget. This stands in contrast to the other wind farm parametrisation scheme introduced by (Fitch et al., 2012). Here $\langle \bar{p}_t \rangle \propto \bar{u}^3$ resulting in a larger value and is not neglected.

3.4 Atmospheric Stability

Three overall classes exist for atmospheric stability: unstable, neutral and stable. These can be further categorised as for instance very stable or very unstable, but for now only these three will be addressed. Unstable flow will become, or already is, turbulent and will remain so, while stable flow will become or will remain laminar, (Stull, 1988). The resulting stability depends on whether the stabilising or destabilising effects surpass each other. In theory, all terms in the energy equation, Equation (3.21), could be evaluated for this purpose. The stability is typically evaluated with only two of the terms in Equation (3.21): Buoyant production (term III) and mechanical (shear) production (term IV).

If the mechanical shear production is much larger than the buoyant, or if the buoyant production is close to zero, the atmospheric stability is neutral. When the buoyant production exceeds the mechanical, either stable or unstable atmospheric conditions will occur.

If heat is released from the ground, i.e. a positive heat flux, or if an air parcel will rise from the ground or sink to the ground and continue to do either, the boundary layer is unstable and turbulence will be enhanced. If heat is transferred to the ground or an air parcel will return to its own starting point, i.e. not continue to travel either upwards or downwards, the boundary layer is stable and turbulence will be suppressed.

As the atmospheric stability can enhance or suppress turbulence, the development of the wind profile is affected by the stability. How so is illustrated in Figure 3.2 for stable, neutral and unstable conditions.

Figure 3.2: Illustration of a stable, neutral and unstable boundary layer.

Usually, when considering the atmospheric stability, the Obukhov length, L , is used. There are slightly different ways of defining this parameter, but for (Stull, 1988), the definition is

$$L = -\frac{\overline{\theta}_v u_*^3}{\kappa g (w' \theta'_v)} \quad (3.24)$$

where θ_v is the virtual potential temperature and θ'_v its fluctuations, u_* the friction velocity, $\kappa = 0.4$ is the von Kármán constant, g the gravitational acceleration and w' the wind speed fluctuations in the vertical direction. Alternative definitions exist where the temperature \overline{T} is used rather than $\overline{\theta}_v$ in the nominator, see (Grachev and Fairall, 1996; Peña et al., 2016), or where the virtual potential

temperature, θ_v , is replaced with the potential temperature θ where

$$\theta = T + (g/C_p) z, \quad \text{and} \quad \theta_v = \theta(1 + 0.61r) \quad (3.25)$$

where $C_p = 1004 \text{ J/kgK}$ is the specific heat and r is the water vapour mixing ratio. The term $\overline{w'\theta'_v}$ is the surface-layer kinematic heat flux. The Obukhov length has the unit meters.

This length scale can be interpreted as the height level where buoyancy will dominate over mechanical production of turbulence and indicates, roughly, when the stability effects become important.

The atmospheric stability can be classified based on L as shown in Table 3.1 as also defined in (Hasager et al., 2009; Peña et al., 2007).

Stability class	Obukhov length interval [m]
Very stable	$10 \leq L \leq 50$
Stable	$50 \leq L \leq 200$
Near stable	$200 \leq L \leq 500$
Neutral	$ L \geq 500$
Near unstable	$-500 \leq L \leq -200$
Unstable	$-200 \leq L \leq -100$
Very unstable	$-100 \leq L \leq -50$

Table 3.1: Atmospheric stability classes with respect to L .

Using the Obukhov length to determine the atmospheric stability can prove difficult, as it is dependent on fluxes and it is not always these are present in measurements. Instead, the bulk Richardson number, Ri_B , can be used. Ri_B is an approximation of the gradient Richardson number, Ri , defined in (Stull, 1988) as

$$Ri = \frac{\frac{g}{\theta_v} \frac{\partial \overline{\theta}_v}{\partial z}}{\left[\left(\frac{\partial \overline{u}}{\partial z} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \overline{v}}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right]} \quad (3.26)$$

where \overline{u} and \overline{v} is the two horizontal components of the wind speed. The nominator is the buoyant production and the denominator as the mechanical production in the flow. To obtain the bulk Richardson number, the following approximations are made:

$$\frac{\partial \overline{\theta}_v}{\partial z} \simeq \frac{\Delta \overline{\theta}_v}{\Delta z}, \quad \frac{\partial \overline{u}}{\partial z} \simeq \frac{\Delta \overline{u}}{\Delta z}, \quad \frac{\partial \overline{v}}{\partial z} \simeq \frac{\Delta \overline{v}}{\Delta z}$$

Furthermore, the difference in wind speed magnitude can be defined as $\Delta \overline{u}_M^2 = \Delta \overline{u}^2 + \Delta \overline{v}^2$. Variations on the bulk Richardson number exists depending for instance on whether $\overline{\theta}_v$, $\overline{\theta}$ or \overline{T} is used. The following definition is from (Peña et al., 2007) which is based on (Grachev and Fairall, 1996)

$$Ri_B = -\frac{g}{\overline{T}_z} \frac{z \Delta \overline{\theta}_v}{\overline{u}_{M,z}^2} \quad (3.27)$$

where \overline{T}_z and $\overline{u}_{M,z}$ is the mean temperature and wind speed measured at height z and $\Delta \overline{\theta}_v$ is the difference in virtual potential temperature between height z and the sea surface. It is a prerequisite for Equation (3.27) that the difference is taken between mean sea level and a height z as it can be

assumed that $u_M = 0$ m/s at the sea surface, yielding $\Delta\bar{u}_M = \bar{u}_{M,z} - \bar{u}_{M,0} = \bar{u}_{M,z}$. The only wind speed measurement needed then is at z .

The bulk Richardson number is related to z/L

$$\frac{z}{L} = \begin{cases} C_1 Ri_B & \text{for unstable conditions} \\ \frac{C_1 Ri_B}{1 - C_2 Ri_B} & \text{for stable conditions} \end{cases} \quad (3.28)$$

as suggested by (Grachev and Fairall, 1996) with $C_1 = 10$ and $C_2 = 5$ where the second term is limited by $0 \leq Ri_B < C_2^{-1}$.

It should be noted that whereas there for the gradient Richardson number, Ri , is a critical value where the flow is known to go from laminar to turbulent or vice versa, no specific critical value exists for the bulk Richardson number, Ri_B , alone. The relations in Equation (3.27) can be used along with the stability classes listed in Table 3.1 to estimate the atmospheric stability as has been done in (Peña et al., 2007; Peña and Hahmann, 2012; Hansen et al., 2012). The basis for these results were that they had access to the sea surface temperature.

Preferably, when computing Ri_B , the level z should not be too high up but rather be close to the sea surface. Otherwise, large gradients that can occur between the two levels can be averaged out.

3.5 Wind Profile

As mentioned, the vertical velocity gradients are implicitly dependent on the atmospheric stability. The velocity profile as a function of z/L can be expressed as

$$\frac{\bar{u}_M}{u_*} = \frac{1}{\kappa} \left[\ln \left(\frac{z}{z_0} \right) + \Psi_M \left(\frac{z}{L} \right) \right] \quad (3.29)$$

from (Stull, 1988) where z_0 is the aerodynamic roughness length and Ψ_M is a function for the atmospheric stability depending on whether it is stable, unstable or neutral. The aerodynamic roughness length is the height where the wind speed becomes zero and is *not* equal to the actual height of the roughness elements. Values for z_0 can be found in literature for different terrains. In (Stull, 1988, fig. 9.6), z_0 is 1 for large cities and forests and between 0.01 and 0.1 for farmland. Over sea the Charnock relationship can be used

$$z_0 = \frac{\alpha_c u_*^2}{g} \quad (3.30)$$

where $\alpha_c = 0.016$. The roughness length is a function of the friction velocity, u_* , as stronger winds makes higher waves resulting in larger u_* .

The dependence on atmospheric stability is expressed via the function Ψ_M . There exist different variations for Ψ_M and they can be found in literature, for instance in (Stull, 1988). For neutral atmospheric conditions $\Psi_M = 0$.

Often the wind profile is shown as $(u, \log(z))$ where a linear relation can be seen if showing the y -axis in logarithmic scale. In that case, Equation (3.29) is rewritten to

$$\ln(z) = \frac{\kappa}{u_*} \bar{u}_M + \ln(z_0) \quad (3.31)$$

for neutral conditions. If a profile for unstable or stable conditions is shown as $(u, \log(z))$, the profile cannot be expected to be linear as illustrated in Figure 3.3 which is due to the term Ψ_M .

Figure 3.3: Illustration of a stable, neutral and unstable boundary layer with logarithmic z -axis. Illustration based on (Stull, 1988, fig. 9.5).

3.6 Wind Farm Efficiency

Conventionally, a wind farm efficiency is defined as

$$\eta = \frac{P_{\text{Net}}}{P_{\text{Gross}}} \quad (3.32)$$

where P_{Net} is the actual power production of the wind farm and P_{Gross} is a reference power production. The gross power production can, for instance, be defined from the power production of one turbine and then multiplied with the number of turbines in operation which yields the net power production: $P_{\text{Gross}} = P_t N_t$ with P_t being the power of the chosen turbine and N_t the number of turbines in operation at that time.

The turbine chosen to estimate P_{Gross} is not necessarily the same at all times as it depends on which criterion is set. It can be the turbine producing the most power at a time, which will always yields a wind farm efficiency below 1. Otherwise, a turbine which is free-standing, i.e. not in a internal wake of the wind farm, can be chosen.

For this project, the wind farm efficiency of Barrow (BOW) will be computed. As it is expected that Barrow will be in the wake of the upstream wind farms a considerable amount of the time, the two methods for choosing a reference turbine are not optimal.

As an alternative, Shell Flats meteorological mast will be used to estimate the gross power production. The wind speed at hub height of turbines in Barrow (75 m) will be interpolated from Shell Flats measurement levels (50 m, 70 m, 80 m and 82 m) using Equation (3.31). The power produced by a turbine in Barrow if it was standing at Shell Flats can be obtained from the wind speed at 75 m and the power curve. The wind farm efficiency for Barrow with respect to Shell Flats is defined as

$$\eta_{SF} = \frac{P_{\text{Net}}}{P_{SF} N_t} \quad (3.33)$$

This method assumes that the wind speed does not change between Shell Flats and Barrow. Furthermore, it is sensitive to any effects on Shell Flats, for instance wakes, and there is a risk of η_{SF} exceeding 1 if that is the case.

3.7 WRF: Model Set Up

The Advanced Research WRF (ARW) (v3.8.1) is a Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) model and used to obtain the wind resources where the area of interest is Barrow Offshore Wind farm (BOW). The upstream wind farms, Walney 1 (WOW01), Walney 2 (WOW02), West of Duddon Sands (WDS) and Ormonde (OOWF), will be modelled using the Explicit Wake Parametrisation (EWP).

The general set up for any WRF simulation consist of one model grid with 3-4 domains nested within one another, with the outer domain being the coarsest and the inner being the finest. The ratio between each domain is recommended to be 3 or 5.

When including wind turbines in a simulation, it is recommended by (Volker et al., 2015) to have one simulation where the inner domain is computed twice: Once with turbines and another without. The advantages is firstly, that you do not have to calculate domain 1 and 2 twice and secondly, that the boundary conditions ought to be the same for domain 3 with and without turbines. However, during the project some unexpected deviations in the inner domain were seen and it was decided to use a different set up. Instead, two simulations are run for each case, one with turbines and one without as illustrated in Figure 3.4 for 3 nested domains.

Figure 3.4: Illustration of domain set up for one case where (a) is the simulation containing turbines and (b) the simulation without.

For this project, a total of 14 simulations were run. Two of these are the main simulation, which are for the wind resource assessment, based on a 1-year simulation and the other 12 are a small study in grid resolution and comparison between the EWP and Fitch parametrisation based on a 1-week simulation. The cases are listed in Table 3.2.

All WRF simulations are run as a real case with initial boundary conditions from the ERA5 reanalysis and OSTIA for the sea surface temperature. The simulations are for the outer domain nudged to the ERA5 reanalysis. The main simulations (EWP-1km-1yr) are run for 1 year with blocks of 11 days including 24 hours spin-up. Each block starts at 00:00:00 UTC. The remaining 1-week simulations run in blocks of 8 days including 24 hours spin up. The same approach as in (Hahmann et al., 2015).

For the grid resolution, the week 14th July through 21st July 2016 will be simulated. For the wind resource assessment, the simulation will run from 1st October 2014 through 30th September 2015.

Resolution	Period	Parametrisation	W/ or w/o WF	Simulation name	Case name
1 km	1 year	EWP	WF	EWP-1km-1yr-WF	EWP-1km-1yr
		EWP	No WF	EWP-1km-1yr-NoWF	
	1 week	EWP	WF	EWP-1km-1wk-WF	EWP-1km-1wk
		EWP	No WF	EWP-1km-1wk-NoWF	
		Fitch	WF	Fitch-1km-1wk-WF	Fitch-1km-1wk
		Fitch	No WF	Fitch-1km-1wk-NoWF	
2 km	1 week	EWP	WF	EWP-2km-1wk-WF	EWP-2km-1wk
		EWP	No WF	EWP-2km-1wk-NoWF	
		Fitch	WF	Fitch-2km-1wk-WF	Fitch-2km-1wk
		Fitch	No WF	Fitch-2km-1wk-NoWF	
3 km	1 week	EWP	WF	EWP-3km-1wk-WF	EWP-3km-1wk
		EWP	No WF	EWP-3km-1wk-NoWF	
		Fitch	WF	Fitch-3km-1wk-WF	Fitch-3km-1wk
		Fitch	No WF	Fitch-3km-1wk-NoWF	

Table 3.2: The 14 WRF simulations for the project. The resolution in the first column refers to the resolution in the inner domain. *WF* or *NoWF* refers to whether the upstream wind farms (WF) are in the simulation or not.

3.7.1 Physics

The same model physics are used in all of the simulations, except regarding the wind farm parametrisation and whether there are turbines in the domain or not. Some of the model physics are listed in Table 3.3. The set up is based on (National Center for Atmospheric Research, 2016) and (Wang et al., 2016) along with the work of (Hahmann et al., 2015; Volker et al., 2015, 2017) and experience from the configuration of the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA).

The simulations have a fixed time step, except the main simulation, EWP-1yr-1km, where adaptive time stepping has been used. Recommendations from (Wang et al., 2016) has been followed for setting up both fixed and adaptive time stepping.

It should be noted that for EWP, it is necessary to set the initial length scale σ_0 which describes the near-wake expansion, (Volker et al., 2015). In this project, $\sigma_0 = 1.7r_0$, with r_0 being the length of the wind turbine blades, which also is used in (Volker et al., 2015, 2017). The value were fitted based on measurements from Horns Rev 1 in (Volker et al., 2015) wherein it is recommended to use the same value for similar turbines. Ideally, the length scale should be fitted to match the conditions for specific turbines and wind farms, but this investigation was not prioritised.

Physic	Configuration	Option	Source
Surface layer:	MYNN surface layer	(5)	NEWA
Planetary boundary layer:	MYNN 2.5 PBL w. TKE advection	(5)	(Volker et al., 2017)
Cumulus Parameterization:	Kain-Fritsch scheme for $\Delta x > 3$ km	(1)	(Hahmann et al., 2015)
Wind farm parametrisation:	Fitch / EWP with $\sigma_0 = 1.7R_0$	(1)/(2)	(Volker et al., 2015, 2017)

Table 3.3: Model physics for WRF model configuration.

3.7.2 Model grid

Three model grids will be set up to run the cases. They will be referred to by the grid spacing of the inner domain. The three model grids are: 1 km, 2 km and 3 km. The domains are set up using the recommendations from (National Center for Atmospheric Research, 2018) and the specifications are listed in Table 3.4. A compromise is made for domain 1 in both the 1 km and 3 km model grid. It is recommended that any domain should at least have a size of 100×100 cells but domain 1 is made smaller as to not cut through a mountainous area. All model grids have 61 vertical levels and the Lambert projection is used. The domains can be seen in Figure 3.5 on a map (Figure 3.5a, 3.5c and 3.5e) with the domains indicated by the boxes. The borders of the maps are not a domain itself.

In Figure 3.5b, 3.5d and 3.5f, the turbines relative to the WRF grid can be seen. Special care has been taken for the 3 km model grid to ensure that one whole grid cell is between West of Duddon Sands and Barrow. Since WOW03 and WOW04 is not included in the analysis, they are not represented in the figures. The same applies for Shell Flats 50 m mast. The colour scheme is the same as in Figure 1.2.

A smaller investigation of the grid spacing and wind farm parametrisation is performed based on the three model grids. It should be noted that the main objective of this project is not to evaluate the two parametrisations which is why the Fitch parametrisation only is used for the 1-week simulations as stated in Table 3.2. Typically, WRF can model the wind resources offshore using a 3×3 km grid, however, lower resolution is also seen in (Lee and Lundquist, 2017; Volker et al., 2015, 2017; Siedersleben et al., 2018).

Domain	1 km		2 km		3 km	
	Resolution [m]	$N_x \times N_y$ [-]	Resolution [m]	$N_x \times N_y$ [-]	Resolution [m]	$N_x \times N_y$ [-]
1	27,000	80×80	18,000	100×100	27,000	55×55
2	9,000	115×130	6,000	151×190	9,000	109×109
3	3,000	130×130	2,000	109×109	3,000	109×109
4	1,000	130×130	-	-	-	-

Table 3.4: Domain specifications for the three model grids with resolution ($\Delta x \times \Delta y$) and $N_x \times N_y$ the number of cells in East-to-West and North-to-South, respectively.

Figure 3.5: The three cases with their respective domains and wind turbines in where (a) and (b) is for the 1 km geogrid, (c) and (d) for the 2 km and (e) and (f) for 3 km.

3.7.3 Wind Farm Parametrisation

For the main simulation, EWP will be used to model the upstream wind farms. For the grid resolution, the Fitch parametrisation will also be used. It is only the upstream wind farms that will be included in WRF simulation. The wind farm to be investigated, Barrow, will *not* be in the simulations. The area to investigate for wind resources occupied by Barrow will be affected by external wakes from the upstream wind farms but not from internal wakes.

For both parametrisations, the power curve and thrust coefficient is needed for any turbine that is to be included in the simulations. The power curve and thrust coefficient provided by Ørsted for West of Duddon Sands, Walney 1 and Walney 2 and DTU Wind Energy for Ormonde are used, see Figure 2.1.

3.7.4 Processing WRF Outputs

WRF works with staggered grids in both the horizontal and vertical direction, meaning that the velocity components for, (u, v, w) , are staggered one-half grid length from the thermodynamic variables θ , which are in the mass points of the grid, (Skamarock et al., 2018). There are four grids: The u -, v -, w - and mass grid. The concept of a staggered grid is shown in Figure 3.6 in both horizontal and vertical direction. The variables on either grid can be interpolated linearly to the other as:

$$\phi_{\text{mp},ijk} = \frac{1}{2} (\phi_{u,ijk} + \phi_{u,(i+1)jk}) \quad (3.34)$$

$$\phi_{\text{mp},ijk} = \frac{1}{2} (\phi_{v,ijk} + \phi_{v,i(j+1)k}) \quad (3.35)$$

$$\phi_{\text{mp},ijk} = \frac{1}{2} (\phi_{w,ijk} + \phi_{w,ij(k+1)}) \quad (3.36)$$

where ϕ can be any variable. The first subscript denotes the grid where the variable is centred in, which on the left hand side is the mass (point) grid and on the right hand side is any of the staggered grids. The second subscript, ijk , denotes the index of the respective grids.

The vertical coordinates are not given in terms of meters above mean sea level but as the non-dimensional parameter η which is a terrain-following hydrostatic coordinate system defined as

$$\eta = \frac{p_h - p_{ht}}{p_{hs} - p_{ht}} \quad (3.37)$$

where p_h is the hydrostatic component of the pressure and p_{ht} and p_{hs} are the values along the top and surface respectively. η ranges from 0 at the top and 1 at the surface. The vertical coordinate system can be seen in Figure 3.7.

The vertical coordinates, z , can be obtained in meters from the base state geopotential (PHB) with unit $[\text{m/s}^2]$, and perturbation geopotential (PH) with unit $[\text{m/s}^2]$, as

$$z = \frac{PHB + PH}{g} \quad (3.38)$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration. Whereas PHB is static and does not change in time, PH varies in time, i.e. the z -coordinate in meters varies in each cell for each time step.

The magnitude of the wind speed, u_M , in a mass point is determined from the two horizontal wind speed components, u and v , as

$$u_M = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2} \quad (3.39)$$

when u and v both have been interpolated to the mass point as well. The wind direction, φ , in one cell is obtained from the wind speed components u and v as

$$\varphi = \tan^{-1}(u/v) + 180^\circ \quad (3.40)$$

where u and v is in the same cell point. This will give the wind direction relative to the cell. In order to get the wind direction relative to the Earth, u and v has to be transformed to being relative to Earth as

$$u_{\text{Earth}} = u \cdot \cos(\alpha) - v \cdot \sin(\alpha), \quad v_{\text{Earth}} = v \cdot \cos(\alpha) + u \cdot \sin(\alpha) \quad (3.41)$$

where α is the map rotation. Both $\cos(\alpha)$ and $\sin(\alpha)$ are WRF output variables. The wind direction relative to Earth can be obtained where using u_{Earth} and v_{Earth} in Equation (3.40).

For determining any variable at a specific height level, linear interpolation is used. For wind speed magnitude, linear interpolation is performed when taking advantage of the linear relationship between u_M and $\ln(z)$ stated in Equation (3.31).

In this project, the relative difference between two simulations will be used to evaluate the difference between them and is computed as

$$\text{Rel. difference} = \frac{\phi_{ijk,WF} - \phi_{ijk,NoWF}}{\phi_{ijk,NoWF}} \quad (3.42)$$

where ϕ is any variable in cell (ijk) and WF or $NoWF$ refers to the simulation with or without upstream wind farms (WF).

Figure 3.6: A staggered grid in the (a) horizontal and (b) vertical direction with the non-dimensional vertical coordinate, η , from (Skamarock et al., 2018). u , v , w and θ are cell centres in their respective grid.

Figure 3.7: Vertical levels in WRF from (Skamarock et al., 2018).

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CHAPTER 4

Preprocessing

In this chapter, preprocessing of the provided data presented in [Chapter 2](#) is reviewed. A data quality control is performed for the two data sets from Shell Flats. This involves defining invalid data and defining one wind speed magnitude for each height level and one wind direction measurement for the mast. Lastly, the general criteria used in this project for comparing different data sources are accounted.

4.1 Data Quality Control: Shell Flats 2011-2012

Before using the data from Shell Flats for analysis, a quality control is performed. The report for the measurement campaign, (Dong Energy / ScottishPower, 2011), is used to identify offsets and invalid measurements. Firstly, all time entries with one or more NaN (not-a-number) values are removed. Secondly, invalid measurements are identified. These are listed for pressure, temperature and relative humidity to be 600 kPa, -40° and 0% respectively. The cup anemometer on the north-west (NW) boom at 80 m was seen to have some extreme values (over 400 m/s). Considering the measurements on the south-east (SE) boom at the same height as well as the measurements from the top of the mast, any measurement larger than 30 m/s is discarded. The ultra sonic anemometer has an offset of 45° for the wind direction, which is corrected for. With these adjustments, the data recovery rate is 97.4%.

4.1.1 Wind Direction

At 78 m there is a wind vane on each boom and at 80 m an ultra sonic anemometer which measures the wind direction. The wind vane at the north-west boom is compared with the ultra sonic anemometer. From Equation (3.4) a mean offset of -12.99° between the two is found. Likewise, a mean bias between the two wind vanes are found to be -6.69° .

In the end, only one instrument should be used to evaluate the wind direction at Shell Flats. To evaluate the instruments at Shell Flats, the SCADA data for Barrow (BOW) are used where a mean wind direction from the farm is obtained. It is assumed that the wind direction does not change significantly between the Barrow and Shell Flats. The difference in wind direction between BOW and each instrument can be seen in Figure 4.1 as a moving average. The averages are computed for every 5th day covering the week before and after. The raw data are shown in Appendix B.

Figure 4.1: The difference in measured wind direction as a moving average between met mast instruments and the computed BOW wind direction

In Table 4.1, the mean bias between BOW and each instrument is listed. It can be seen that the difference is smallest for the ultra sonic anemometer. However, as the ultra sonic anemometer is not on Shell Flats for the later data set (2014-2015), this instrument will not be used. If using the wind vanes, the reference instrument will be the same type for each data set. The wind direction for SE boom and NW boom can be corrected with -6° and -12° respectively. With the smaller bias, the vane on the SE boom will be used as the reference for the wind direction at Shell Flats 2011-2012.

	BOW - sonic	BOW - vane (NW)	BOW - vane (SE)
Mean bias [°]	-0.10	-12.60	-6.17

Table 4.1: Mean bias corresponding to Figure 4.1.

4.1.2 Wind Speed

The wind speed measurements are sensitive to the tower construction. An instrument will underestimate the wind speed if the wind comes through the tower. With the information on the tower construction, it is expected that disruptions will be seen at approximately 135° and 315° .

These sensitivities are investigated for at each level, at first, where there are two booms orientated opposite, i.e. an NW and SE boom. For each level, the fraction u_{SE}/u_{NW} can be computed with respect to the wind direction measurements for each vane and also the corrected wind direction (SE boom). In Figure 4.2 to Figure 4.4, the wind speed fractions as a moving average for every degree with a width of $\pm 2.5^\circ$ are shown. It can for each be seen that the anemometer on the SE boom measures lower winds from the north-west whereas the anemometer on the NW boom measures lower wind wind from south-east. In the left panel, the disruptions in the flow is offset with respect to where it is expected to be, 135° and 315° respectively. The corrected wind direction, the right panel, corresponds better with what is expected.

With reference to the right side panel in Figure 4.2 to Figure 4.4, one wind speed for each level is computed, u_{50} , u_{70} and u_{80} respectively. In general, the average between the two instruments is used. But for ranges with flow distortion, either the SE anemometer or NW anemometer is used. Which instrument is used is listed in Table 4.2.

	SE anemometer is used [°]	NW anemometer is used [°]
50 m	[115 – 160]	[295 – 335]
70 m	[115 – 160]	[295 – 335]
80 m	[120 – 155]	[300 – 300]

Table 4.2: Choosing which anemometer to use for each level in critical ranges.

Lastly, the wind speed measurements at 82 m are considered. It might not be expected to have any obvious flow disruptions as the instrument is placed on the top. In Figure 4.5, the ratio between the computed u_{80} and the measured wind speeds at 82 m with respect to the wind direction is shown. It can be seen that at approximately 130° , a disruption is experienced by the anemometer at the top. The disruption can be due to a construction element of the tower which causes the anemometer to be sheltered. The wind speed at 82 m, u_{82} , will be set equal to the anemometer measurements at 82 m, except in the range $120 - 155^\circ$, where the anemometer at 80 m on the SE boom will be used.

Figure 4.2: (a) u_{50mSE}/u_{50mNW} with respect to the NW vane and the SE vane and (b) u_{50mSE}/u_{50mNW} with respect to the corrected vane on the SE boom.

Figure 4.3: (a) u_{70mSE}/u_{70mNW} with respect to the NW vane and the SE vane and (b) u_{70mSE}/u_{70mNW} with respect to the corrected vane on the SE boom.

Figure 4.4: (a) u_{80mSE}/u_{80mNW} with respect to the NW vane and the SE vane and (b) u_{80mSE}/u_{80mNW} with respect to the corrected vane on the SE boom.

Figure 4.5: u_{80}/u_{82Top} with respect to the corrected vane on the SE boom.

4.2 Data Quality Control: Shell Flats 2014-2015

As with the previous data set, the quality of the Shell Flats 2014-2015 data set is controlled. Missing values are discarded along with any other measurements at the corresponding time. The new cup anemometer on the north-west boom is not in operation until July 2015. Hence, the instrument will be discarded and only the cup anemometer on the south-east boom which covers the entire period will be used.

Some of the measurements performed by the cup anemometer at 80 m on the south-east boom are close to 0 m/s but not qualified as missing data per default. A lower threshold of 0.5 m/s is set for wind speeds measured by this instrument. Any data below the threshold are neglected along with other data at the corresponding time.

For all the measurements, there is a gap from 21st June to 14th July 2015. This is likely due to the installation of the new cup anemometer which starts to record wind speeds on 14th July 2015. The data recovery rate is 90.89%.

4.2.1 Wind Direction

The wind direction is evaluated for the two wind vanes on the north-west and south-east boom. As with the previous data set they have a bias. The bias between the two instrument is on average -4.65° which is slightly lower than what it was in the previous data set (-6.69°).

The mean wind direction from Barrow (BOW) SCADA is used once again to evaluate the wind direction from the two instruments and can be seen in Figure 4.6. The raw data can be seen in Appendix C. It is noted that from July 2015, the two wind vanes have a reduced bias with respect to each other. This corresponds to when the cup anemometer was installed. Either the vanes have been recalibrated or new vanes have been installed when the anemometer was installed.

The mean difference between Barrow and the NW vane is -13.4° and -8.9° between Barrow and the SE vane. As the bias is smaller throughout the year for the SE vane, this instrument will be used as a reference for the wind direction. The measurements are corrected with the offset for -9° .

Figure 4.6: The difference in measured wind direction between met mast instruments and the computed BOW wind direction.

4.2.2 Wind Speed

The wind speed measurements are compared for each orientation at each level, i.e. u_{50mSE}/u_{50mNW} and u_{70mSE}/u_{70mNW} . For the remaining wind speed measurements at 80 m and 82 m, the fraction u_{80mSE}/u_{82mTop} is considered. The moving average for every degree with bin width $\pm 2.5^\circ$ with respect to the wind direction is shown in Figure 4.7 through 4.9 with respect to the NW and SE wind vane (left panel) and for the corrected wind direction (right panel). Based on the figures in the right panel, one single wind speed can be computed at each respective level. At 50 m and 70 m, the mean wind speed measurement between the NW and SE anemometer will be used. When there flow disturbances, one of the instruments are chosen. Table 4.3 lists the wind direction ranges where just one instrument is chosen.

At 80 m, the measurements from the one anemometer at the SE boom will be used but supplemented with measurements from the 82 m anemometer if there are disturbances. The range where the top anemometer is used is $295^\circ - 335^\circ$. The reverse applies for the 82 m wind speed where the 80 m anemometer is used in the range $25^\circ - 92^\circ$.

	SE anemometer is used [$^\circ$]	NW anemometer is used [$^\circ$]
50 m	[112 – 166]	[290 – 340]
70 m	[115 – 165]	[290 – 330]

Table 4.3: Choosing which anemometer to use for each level in critical ranges.

A few things should be noted regarding u_{80mSE}/u_{82mTop} . First of all, the disturbance on the top anemometer has moved from the previous period, where a flow disturbance was seen around 130° , to 45° . This indicates that an element has been moved and is now shadowing the anemometer from a different angle. Secondly, the wind speed fraction varies more than what is seen at the other levels. This is further confirmed when plotting the wind speed fractions with respect to the wind direction but without averaging. In Figure 4.10, the wind speed fraction u_{80mSE}/u_{82mTop} is shown with both the original data and the corrected, i.e. when the 80 m wind speed supplements the 82 m wind speed in critical ranges and vice versa. See Appendix C for corresponding u_{50mSE}/u_{50mNW} and u_{70mSE}/u_{70mNW} . To further clean up the data, any measurement for u_{80mSE} and u_{82mTop} beyond 4 times the standard deviation ($\pm 4\sigma$) in Figure 4.10 (with respect to the corrected data) is removed.

This last action reduces the recovery rate to 89.93%.

Figure 4.7: (a) u_{50mSE}/u_{50mNW} with respect to the NW vane and the SE vane and (b) u_{50mSE}/u_{50mNW} with respect to the corrected vane on the SE boom.

Figure 4.8: (a) u_{70mSE}/u_{70mNW} with respect to the NW vane and the SE vane and (b) u_{70mSE}/u_{70mNW} with respect to the corrected vane on the SE boom.

Figure 4.9: (a) u_{80mSE}/u_{82mTop} with respect to the NW vane and the SE vane and (b) u_{80mSE}/u_{82mTop} with respect to the corrected vane on the SE boom.

Figure 4.10: The wind speed fraction u_{80mSE}/u_{82mTop} with respect to wind direction. Mean and standard deviation is based on the corrected data.

4.3 Comparison of Different Data Sources

Depending on the which data sources are compared with each other, different approaches are used. For the climatology, where a meteorological mast (Shell Flats) and WRF data from the New European Wind Atlas are compared, they are synchronised in time, i.e. only data for common time stamps are included. The same approach is used when analysing SCADA with respect to the Shell Flats.

When comparing SCADA with the main WRF simulation for the wind resource assessment, the data sources are *not* synchronised in time. As mentioned in Chapter 1, it is not of important whether WRF and SCADA have the same conditions for wind speed and direction at the same time. It is the distribution from the two data sources that will be analysed. The comparison between WRF and SCADA will be filtered for conditions, e.g. same wind speed or direction range.

From WRF, a time series has been extracted for each location corresponding to a turbine in Barrow and Shell Flats. This gives a similar set up as the SCADA data.

Below are listed the general requirements for the data for analysis:

- Wind speed is within 4-14 m/s unless otherwise stated.
- When considering a selected number of turbines, they must all be operational at the same time.
- Barrow is at least 90% operational.
- The upstream wind farms are at least 90% operational (if present).
- SCADA: Shell Flats is used as reference for wind direction and speed unless otherwise stated.
- WRF: Reference for wind direction and speed is the Shell Flats cell unless otherwise stated.

The limit in wind speed is as to not compare turbines that are all operating at rated wind speed with the same power production.

The upstream wind farms must also be at least 90% operational, otherwise, the results might contain data for when Barrow is not subject to wind farm wakes.

It should be noted that WRF assumes all turbines to be operating as long as the wind speed is above cut-in and below cut-out wind speed. Hence, no criterion of availability is needed for WRF.

For processing data, mainly MATLAB2018a/b and MATLAB2015b have been used.

Results and Discussion

The climatology in the Irish Sea will first be presented to state the general climatology and to verify that WRF can estimate it. The climatology is evaluated for wind speed and direction and atmospheric stability. Next, the impact from the upstream wind farms on Barrow is shown based on wind farm data (SCADA) which is available both before and after any of the upstream wind farms. The results for the small study in WRF resolution are presented before evaluating the results from the main WRF simulation for the wind resources. In the end, the validation for the wind resources and an estimate on the annual energy production is presented.

5.1 Climatology in the Irish Sea

This section serves firstly, for stating the general climatology in the Irish Sea, and secondly, to see whether WRF can be used to estimate it. For the comparison, the Shell Flats 2011-2012 and the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA, WRF data) data sets have been utilised.

5.1.1 General Climatology

The mean wind speed at Barrow hub height, 75 m, is shown in Figure 5.1 for the Irish Sea. The mean is provided from NEWA and is based on wind speed fields from 2001-2017. The wind speed in the Irish Sea reaches almost 12 m/s but decreases closer to the coast down to 7 m/s. The cluster of wind farms are subject to mean wind speed of 8-10 m/s.

Figure 5.1: Mean offshore wind speed in the Irish Sea and around the cluster of wind farms.

In Figure 5.2a and 5.3a, the wind roses are shown for Shell Flats at 70 and 80 meters respectively. Figure 5.2b and 5.3b shows the NEWA results at 75 meters. Unfortunately, the NEWA output does not have results at the same levels as Shell Flats.

From the wind roses, it can be seen that WRF (NEWA), as Shell Flats, indicates that the prevailing wind direction is from south-west to north-west. Hardly any wind can be expected from north to north-east. Shell Flats also indicates that winds often come from south-east (approximately 160°) which WRF predicts to a lesser degree. This can be due to the spatial resolution of WRF which might average out more local phenomena.

It can also be seen how WRF underestimates the frequency of the larger wind speeds. This is more evident in Figure 5.2a and 5.2b. The NEWA wind rose hardly shows any wind speeds above 25 m/s, whereas Shell Flats indicates that some wind speeds were measured to be above 25 m/s, at lower levels even, especially from south-west at 220° .

Figure 5.2: Wind rose from (a) Shell Flats mast at 70 m and (b) WRF NEWA results at 75 m.

Figure 5.3: Wind rose from (a) Shell Flats mast at 80 m and (b) WRF NEWA results at 75 m.

Figure 5.4a shows the mean wind profile from WRF and Shell Flats measurements. The grey line, dashed and dotted for WRF and Shell Flats respectively, is a fit on the neutral wind profile, Equation (3.29) with $\Psi_M = 0$. As stated, WRF does not capture the stronger winds which is further confirmed by the wind profiles, where Shell Flats shows stronger wind speeds at each level. At 50 m, both WRF and Shell Flats have wind speed data/measurements. The mean wind speed is measured to be 0.32% higher than what WRF predicts. This difference increases at higher levels. Between the levels 75 m - 105 m, the measurements show larger wind speed but by no more than 2% compared to WRF. This is evaluated based upon the neutral wind profile fit. Having the profile underestimated in wind speeds is also seen in (Badger et al., 2016; Floors et al., 2016; Olsen et al., 2017) for offshore sites.

In Figure 5.4b, the correlation between WRF and Shell Flats wind speed at 50 m can be seen. Until 10 m/s, WRF shows smaller wind speeds than measured, and after, WRF shows larger wind speed when relying on the slope of 0.93. The Pearson correlation coefficient is $\rho = 0.88$. This is contradictory to what has previously been observed. There are a few samples, where WRF predicts wind speeds between 20 m/s and 25 m/s where Shell Flats has observed 8 m/s to 15 m/s which can influence the correlation.

Figure 5.4: (a) The mean wind profile from WRF and Shell Flats and (b) the relationship between WRF and Shell Flats at 50 m with $\rho = 0.88$.

5.1.2 Atmospheric Stability

Next, the atmospheric stability is compared between Shell Flats and WRF. If possible, the Obukhov length, L , is used for this type of comparison. In order to compute L from measurements, the fluxes w' and θ' or θ'_v are needed. As these are not measured at Shell Flats, the atmospheric stability will, first, be evaluated with the bulk Richardson number, Ri_B , from Equation (3.28) but with $\Delta\bar{\theta}$ rather than $\Delta\bar{\theta}_v$ for simplicity. This requires temperature and wind speed measurements. Shell Flats have temperature measurements at platform height and 82 m and wind speed at 82 m. WRF temperatures will be linearly interpolated to the same levels. The same goes for WRF wind speed, but where the linear relationship between u and $\log(z)$ is used from Equation (3.31).

The bulk Richardson number, Ri_B , is compared with respect to their distribution. It does, for this investigation, not matter whether the atmospheric stability matches at each specific time, but rather if they show the same distribution.

The Ri_B can be seen in Figure 5.5a. The distributions do not match well. This can be due to other reasons than WRF not being able to compute the atmospheric stability properly. As stated previously in Chapter 3, other research where Ri_B is used for comparison, was based on sea surface temperature and measurements at lower levels, such as 10 meters. The instrumentation of Shell Flats is not ideal for this kind of comparison.

Instead of using Ri_B to compare atmospheric stability, it is assumed that $Ri_B \propto \Delta\bar{\theta}/u_M^2$. This gives an indication of the heat fluxes versus the wind speed. The result can be seen in Figure 5.5b. Here the distributions between Shell Flats and WRF match better than what is seen in Figure 5.5a. The correlation between WRF and NEWA is also computed for both Ri_B and $\Delta\theta/u^2$ in Figure 5.5c and 5.5d, respectively. Figure 5.5d does not indicate a good correlation between WRF and Shell Flats despite the better match in distributions (Figure 5.5b). The correlation for Ri_B is better, but WRF should not be relied on solely for an analysis of atmospheric stability.

Figure 5.5: Distribution of (a) Bulk Richardson Number (Ri_B) and (b) the variable $\Delta\theta/u^2$. Figure (c) and (d) shows the relationship between mast and WRF for Ri_B and $\Delta\theta/u_M^2$ respectively.

5.1.3 Summary

Being at approximately 54° degree latitude, the Irish Sea is expected to be dominated by the westerlies. This is confirmed by Figure 5.2b and 5.3b where the dominating wind is seen to be from the west. WRF does compute a comparable wind climatology when considering wind speed, even though WRF does not compute the larger wind speeds. From Figure 5.4b. it can be seen that wind speeds are not only comparable on long term but also for short-term.

The atmospheric stability did not compare as well as the wind direction and wind speed. Only when considering the distribution of $\Delta\theta/u_M^2$, did the atmospheric stability prove to be similar in distribution between WRF and Shell Flats. This is likely due to the instrumentation of the mast rather than WRF not being able to simulate the atmospheric stability. Utilising the bulk Richardson number for evaluating atmospheric stability has also been performed by (Peña et al., 2007; Peña and Hahmann, 2012; Hansen et al., 2012). Their results were based on measurements between the sea surface and 10 meter above mean sea level whereas measurements at 10 m and 80 m were utilised for this analysis. When computing Ri_B over a large vertical distance, there is a risk that gradients are averaged out and the result is not reliable.

5.2 Wake Losses Based on SCADA

Before analysing WRF results, SCADA data are assessed to see if they reveal how Barrow is being subject to external wake loss by upstream wind farms (WF).

5.2.1 Turbine Power Production

The power production between two turbines are considered to analyse wake effects from the upstream wind farms. Two turbines from Barrow, D01 and D08, are used which are located in each end of the row facing West of Duddon Sands. The two turbines can be seen in Figure 5.6. If consulting the map introducing the wind farm location and layout in Figure 1.2, it can be assumed that when the wind comes from south-west, D08 will in the wake from upstream wind farms while D01 will not. When the wind comes from west, both turbines should be in the wake.

The turbine power production will be computed for prior the construction of the upstream wind farms (July 2011 - August 2012) and after (October 2014 - November 2015). As reference for wind direction, the computed mean direction for Barrow is used, and the nacelle anemometer is used to fulfil the criterion for wind speed range.

Figure 5.6: Turbine D01 and D08 marked in BOW layout.

The power production of D01 normalised with D08 is shown in Figure 5.7. The grey areas in the figure mark the internal wake effects in Barrow. Within these ranges, the turbine power production of the two turbines corresponds well with what is expected from internal wake effects from the wind farm layout, see Figure 5.6. From Figure 5.8, it can be seen that the ranges for internal wake effects are not strongly affected between the two periods 2011-2012 to 2014-2015, indicating no effect from the upstream wind farms.

From 220° to 276° , D01 produced more than D08. At 246° D01 produces 50% more than D08 which is an increase of 43% after the upstream wind farms have been commissioned.

Before the upstream wind farms were commissioned, D01 was seen to produce up to 27% more than D08 between 260° and 300° . There is no apparent reason for this, as the flow ought to be undisturbed from this range in this period. After the upstream wind farms are commissioned, D01

produces up to 28% more in the same range. The peak has moved from 288° to 271° . This can be due to the layout of West of Duddon Sands as there within it is an open area. When the wind comes from west, the turbine D01 has fewer turbines in front than D08 has.

Figure 5.7: Turbine power production of D01 normalised with power production of D08.

Figure 5.8: Relative difference in turbine power fraction with reference to before the upstream wind farms were in operation.

5.2.2 Wind Farm Efficiency

Next, the wind farm efficiency, η_{SF} , is considered for Barrow (BOW) using Equation (3.33). The efficiency is computed when only using free standing and when using all available turbines in BOW. Shell Flats (SF) is used as reference for wind speed and direction.

Figure 5.9 shows the wind farm efficiency when using only free standing turbines and when including all operational turbines. Figure 5.10 shows the relative difference of η_{SF} with reference to before the upstream wind farms were in operation. It should be noted that for the relative difference, using either free standing turbines or all turbines results in the same relative change in efficiency compared to before the upstream wind farms were commissioned.

The effect on the wind farm efficiency for Barrow due to the upstream wind farms can be seen in both Figure 5.9 and Figure 5.10.

For the free standing turbines, Figure 5.9a and Figure 5.10, the efficiency drops from a minimum of 84.8% to 66.9% in the range 245° to 285° . The range corresponds to when the wind comes through West of Duddon Sands before reaching Barrow. The lowest efficiency of 66.9% occurs for 269° which is a relative decrease of 24.7% compared to before the upstream wind farm were build. The largest relative decrease in efficiency is seen for 256° where it has decreased with 28.2%.

When including all turbines in the analysis, Figure 5.9b and Figure 5.10, the results are similar. The largest relative decrease in efficiency is also found at 256° but is 30.5%. The lowest efficiency is 63.1 at 269° which is a relative decrease of 24.8%.

The advantage of only using free standing turbines is that internal wake effects will be excluded which can be seen in Figure 5.9a and 5.9b in the range 130° to 180° where Figure 5.9b shows internal wake effects, but 5.9a does not.

In Chapter 3, it was mentioned that there is a risk of η_{SF} exceeding 1 when Shell Flats is used as a reference for the gross power. This is evident in both Figure 5.9a and 5.9b in the ranges 0° to 130° , 185° to 230° and 285° to 325° .

Both the first and second range (0° to 130° and 185° to 230°), is marked as being due to external effects. The efficiency above one is seen for both analyses and both before and after the upstream wind farms have been commissioned. At 16° and 17° , the wind farm efficiency has increased by 80.3% and 87.2% for free standing and all turbines, respectively. It is still assumed to be due external or land effects as Barrow is close to the coast.

In the second range (285° to 325°), Shell Flats itself is presumed to be subject to wind farm wakes. The wind direction corresponds with the location of Walney 1, Walney 2 and West of Duddon Sands with respect to Shell Flats. In the same wind direction, Barrow is only subject to wakes from Ormonde.

Figure 5.9: The wind farm efficiency for Barrow based on (a) free standing turbines and (b) all turbines.

Figure 5.10: The relative difference in wind farm efficiency with reference to before the upstream wind farms were in operation.

To visualise the wind farm efficiency and how it is affected by the surroundings, η_{SF} for free standing turbines from 2014-2015 is plotted around Shell Flats and Barrow centre in Figure 5.11. The colours used for the wind farm efficiency corresponds to the same colours used to indicate external effects, wake effects on Barrow and wake effects on Shell Flats (purple, yellow and blue) in Figure 5.9a.

Considering first the sections where Barrow has a wind farm efficiency above 1, most can be explained by the terrain. When the wind comes from north-east, Shell Flats is sheltered by the coast. At 200° , it is presumed Shell Flats must be subject to an unknown external effect. The flow is undisturbed for approximately 50 km, when the wind comes from 200° . It seems questionable that the coast alone results in the wind farm efficiency increasing one.

The third section, where $1 < \eta_{SF}$ is centred around 307° . Based on Figure 5.11a, it seems correct to assume that Shell Flats will be subject to wind farm wakes. Figure 5.11b indicated that Barrow will not be affected greatly by wind farm wakes when the wind comes from 307° . It corresponds to the wind going between Ormonde and Walney 1 and Walney 2 before reaching Barrow.

Barrow experiences a decrease in wind farm efficiency, when the wind comes through West of Duddon Sands at 270° as can be seen in Figure 5.11b.

5.2.3 Summary

A decrease in the efficiency for Barrow can be seen after the upstream wind farms have started operating. This can be seen when considering the power production of individual turbines, D01 and D08 in this case, where D08 produces 50% less due to being subject to wind farm wakes. The wind farm efficiency of Barrow is observed to decrease up to 30.5% based on all turbines and 28.3% based on free standing turbines when the wind comes through West of Duddon Sands (245° to 285°). When the wind farm efficiency is defined with reference to Shell Flats, the efficiency is sometimes observed to be above one. This is not due to Barrow being efficient, but rather a results of Shell Flats being subject to wakes or is sheltered.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.11: The wind farm efficiency (BOW) for free standing turbines 2014-2015 as shown in Figure 5.9a placed around (a) Shell Flats and (b) centre of BOW. The colours, purple, yellow and blue corresponds to the areas marked in Figure 5.9a with the same colours. The black dashed line indicates when $\eta_{SF} = 1$.

5.3 WRF Resolution

The grid resolution to use in WRF is tested on three different model grids as defined in Table 3.4. The three model grids are simulating the same week, with and without a wind farm.

Please note, that it is only the upstream wind farms (OOWF, WDS, WOW01 and WOW02) that is in the WRF simulations. Barrow (BOW) is not since the area is treated as a potential for a new wind farm. All figures in this section are shown at $z = 75$ m which is the hub height of the BOW turbines. There are no filter in wind speed for this analysis.

5.3.1 Wind Speed and Direction

The wind speed and wind direction in one cell is considered first. The cell corresponds to where Shell Flats is located. In Figure 5.12a and 5.12b, the wind speed and wind direction at Barrow hub height is shown for the simulations containing upstream wind farms. In order to enhance visibility, a scalar has been added to each time series. Similar plots for simulations without the upstream wind farms can be seen in Appendix D.

The largest variations between the simulations are on July 20th 2016. This is also where the largest variations in wind speed and direction occurs. On July 18th, there are some variations between the simulations for the wind direction but not for the wind speed. The mean difference in wind speed and direction is listed in Table 5.1 between the simulations. To determine wind direction differences, Equation (3.4) has been used. The differences are very small for both wind speed and direction. It is reassuring to see that there is no difference in using EWP or Fitch when no upstream wind farms are in the simulation. From these observations, it can be assumed that the two parametrisations do not affect the incoming flow environment.

Difference between	Wind speed [m/s]	Wind direction [°]
EWP: (1km-1wk-WF) - (1km-1wk-NoWF)	$-9.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.07
EWP: (2km-1wk-WF) - (2km-1wk-NoWF)	$-28.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-0.04
EWP: (3km-1wk-WF) - (3km-1wk-NoWF)	$-35.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.11
Fitch: (1km-1wk-WF) - (1km-1wk-NoWF)	$-1.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.18
Fitch: (2km-1wk-WF) - (1km-1wk-NoWF)	$-27.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-0.02
Fitch: (3km-1wk-WF) - (1km-1wk-NoWF)	$-40.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.01
(EWP-1km-1wk-WF) - (Fitch-1km-1wk-WF)	$-7.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-0.11
(EWP-2km-1wk-WF) - (Fitch-2km-1wk-WF)	$-1.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-0.02
(EWP-3km-1wk-WF) - (Fitch-3km-1wk-WF)	$-4.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.10
(EWP-1km-1wk-NoWF) - (Fitch-1wk-1km-NoWF)	0.00	0.00
(EWP-2km-1wk-NoWF) - (Fitch-1wk-2km-NoWF)	0.00	0.00
(EWP-3km-1wk-NoWF) - (Fitch-1wk-3km-NoWF)	0.00	0.00

Table 5.1: Mean difference in wind speed and direction between the different simulations.

In Table 5.2, the mean and standard deviation for the wind speed is listed. For the same model grid, it makes little difference whether there are any upstream wind farms or which parametrisation is used. The standard deviation remains roughly the same for all cases and remains within the

Figure 5.12: The (a) wind speed and (b) direction in the Shell Flats cell. Simulations contain upstream wind farms. A scalar is added to each time series to enhance visibility.

range of 2.87 ± 0.04 m/s, with the 2 km model grid having the highest standard deviations. The mean values for each model grid is: 7.64 to 7.65 m/s (1 km), 8.04 to 8.07 m/s (2 km) and 8.02 to 8.07 m/s (3 km), indicating that when using a higher resolution, the mean wind speed can be expected to be less in one cell compared to a 3×3 km cell.

Simulation	Mean [m/s]	Standard deviation [m/s]
EWP-1km-1wk-WF	7.64	2.84
EWP-1km-1wk-NoWF	7.65	2.85
Fitch-1km-1wk-WF	7.65	2.84
Fitch-1km-1wk-NoWF	7.65	2.85
EWP-2km-1wk-WF	8.04	2.90
EWP-2km-1wk-NoWF	8.07	2.91
Fitch-2km-1wk-WF	8.05	2.90
Fitch-2km-1wk-NoWF	8.07	2.91
EWP-3km-1wk-WF	8.02	2.84
EWP-3km-1wk-NoWF	8.07	2.84
Fitch-3km-1wk-WF	8.02	2.83
Fitch-3km-1wk-NoWF	8.07	2.84

Table 5.2: Mean and standard deviation for the wind speed in the Shell Flats cell.

5.3.2 Wind Field

The mean relative difference in the wind fields are shown in Figure 5.13. In Figure 5.13, the upstream wind farms are shown as black circles, Shell Flats as a black square and Barrow as purple circles.

A common difference, regardless of grid resolution, between EWP and Fitch in Figure 5.13, is the shape of the wake. For EWP, two main wakes can be seen: One behind Walney 1, Walney 2 and Ormonde and another behind West of Duddon Sands which hits Barrow. For Fitch, it looks as if there is only one main wake which is centred behind Walney 1, Walney 2 and Ormonde. Barrow is still in the wake but not in one as strong as with EWP. The strongest wake impact on Barrow is listed in Table 5.3 with $\pm 0.5\%$ based on the Figure 5.13. The Fitch parametrisation shows weaker wind farm wake impact on Barrow than EWP for all resolutions.

Parametrisation	Grid resolution		
	1 km	2 km	3 km
EWP wake impact	-6.5%	-5.5%	-5.5%
Fitch wake impact	-3.5%	-3.5%	-3.5%

Table 5.3: Largest wake impact on Barrow from Figure 5.13 $\pm 0.5\%$.

The largest difference in the shape of the wind farm wake can be seen between 2 km and 3 km model grids for both parametrisations. Between 1 km and 2 km, the wakes have similar shapes but with the 1 km grid showing more details due to the higher resolution. In Figure 5.13a and 5.13d, a smaller area of positive relative difference can be seen, but it is no larger than 3%.

In Figure 5.14, the relative difference in wind speed is shown for the most frequently occurring wind direction in the simulation, $270 \pm 15^\circ$. The wind direction is obtained from the cell containing Shell Flats. All of the wakes reach the coast which is approximately 25-30 km from the nearest turbine in Barrow. The Fitch parametrisation yields a narrower wake and it looks as if they turn slightly more north as they go towards the coast. Volker et al. (2015) identified similar behaviour, but where the wake computed from the EWP scheme turned towards North due to the Coriolis force. The wake computed from the Fitch scheme in the same study turned South rather than North. This stands in contradiction to what is seen in Figure 5.14 where the wakes computed by the Fitch scheme are seen to turn North. However, this can also be an effect of the terrain pushing the wake. The EWP scheme results in a stronger wake behind West of Duddon Sands which can cause a different far wake behaviour.

The largest wake impact on Barrow can be investigated for the dominating wind direction and is listed in Table 5.4. EWP yields larger wind speed deficit compared to Fitch and whereas the wake deficit from the WP scheme has decreased by 4-5 percentage point, Fitch has only decreased with one.

Parametrisation	Grid resolution		
	1 km	2 km	3 km
EWP wake impact	-9.5%	-9.5%	-8.5%
Fitch wake impact	-4.5%	-4.5%	-4.5%

Table 5.4: Largest wake impact on Barrow from Figure 5.14 $\pm 0.5\%$.

Figure 5.13: The mean relative difference in wind speed for the different model grids and parametrizations for cases (a) EWP-1km-1wk, (b) EWP-2km-1wk, (c) EWP-3km-1wk, (d) Fitch-1km-1wk, (e) Fitch-2km-1wk and (f) Fitch-3km-1wk. Legend: Upstream wind farms in simulation (●), BOW (●) and Shell Flats (■).

Figure 5.14: The mean relative difference in wind speed when wind is coming from west ($270 \pm 15^\circ$) for cases (a) EWP-1km-1wk, (b) EWP-2km-1wk, (c) EWP-3km-1wk, (d) Fitch-1km-1wk, (e) Fitch-2km-1wk and (f) Fitch-3km-1wk. Legend: Upstream wind farms in simulation (\bullet), BOW (\circ) and Shell Flats (\blacksquare). The arrow indicates the wind direction.

5.3.3 Computational Time

For making a larger analysis, it is necessary to consider the computational time. The computational time is not going to be analysed in detail here, but it does deserve some attention. It is based on the six cases used to analyse the grid resolution, which is based on an 8 day simulation (including 24 hours spin-up time) on 8 nodes. An approximate wall time experienced for each model grid is listed in Table 5.5. The wall time increases linearly with increased resolution.

It is a substantial amount of time that can be saved when going to a cruder resolution, but it has to be evaluated against what the objective of the simulation is. There is no purpose in using a crude grid to save time, if the resolution is not good enough to solve the objective.

The numbers in Table 5.5 is based on few simulations and a larger and more extensive study could be made regarding computational time and grid resolution.

	1 km	2 km	3 km
Approx. wall time [hours]	60	40	20

Table 5.5: Approximate used wall time for each model grid for a 7-day simulation (excluding 24 hours spin-up time) on 8 nodes.

5.3.4 Summary

When considering one cell which is not strongly affected by wind farm wakes, the wind speed and direction is approximately equal regardless of grid resolution and wind farm parametrisation. The two wind farm parametrisations do not affect the incoming flow environment.

The difference between using a 1 km or 2 km is not as big compared to using a 2 km or 3 km model grid. EWP yields a stronger wake regardless of distribution. The wakes produced by the Fitch parametrisation are more narrow and tend to be turning northwards compared to the EWP wakes.

The purpose of this project is not to validate both parametrisations, but it is worth noting the different results. The documentation for using the Fitch parametrisation in WRF recommends that the resolution should not be larger than 5 times the rotor diameter. The smallest rotor diameter of all the wind turbines is Barrow on 90 m and the largest is Ormonde with a diameter of 126 m, see Table 1.1. The recommended resolution for Fitch is then 450-630 m. If the Fitch scheme was to be utilised for this study, it would have been necessary to investigate for a higher resolution of 500×500 m. It was decided not to test any grid spacing below 1 km for this project.

When choosing a grid resolution, it is important to consider the computational time. Even though it would be favourable to use the 3 km model grid with respect to time, the previous results indicate that a 1 or 2 km grid is preferable. For the main simulation to obtain the wind resources, it is decided to use the 1 km model grid for better precision and because the necessary resources were available.

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5.4 WRF analysis

The following analysis is based on the main WRF simulations for the wind resource assessment. The analysis covers one year, October 2014 through September 2015. In the simulation, only the upstream wind farms (OOWF, WDS, WOW01 and WOW02) are included. The area occupied by Barrow (BOW) is evaluated but the wind farm itself is not included in the WRF simulation. As a reference for wind direction, the cell where Shell Flats is located is used. All below figures are shown at $z = 75\text{m}$ which is the hub height of the turbines in Barrow. There is no filter in wind speed for this section unless otherwise stated.

5.4.1 Wind Field

The mean wind speed field is shown in Figure 5.15 as the relative difference. It can be seen that a decrease in wind speed is predicted around the wind farms but also an increase in wind speed in the general area which is not expected. The increased wind speed is in the order $1.5 \pm 0.5\%$ to $4.5 \pm 0.5\%$. It is not certain whether these positive differences are due to the wind farm parametrisation or an error during post processing. When just considering the decrease of wind speed around the wind farms, WRF predicts the wind speed around Barrow will decrease with up to $2.5 \pm 0.5\%$. The larger part of Barrow is predicted to experience a decrease in wind speed of $1.5 \pm 0.5\%$. This does not indicate a strong loss in annual energy production.

Figure 5.15: The average relative difference in wind speed with reference to EWP-1yr-1km-NoWF where (b) is a zoom in on (a) marked as the block box. Legend: Upstream wind farms in simulation (\bullet), BOW (\bullet) and Shell Flats (\blacksquare).

The mean wind speed deficit is investigated for every 10 degree with respect to wind direction. Only some of these will be shown in this section and the rest can be found in Appendix E.

In Figure 5.16, the mean wind speed deficit is shown for the directions $20\pm 7.5^\circ$, $40\pm 7.5^\circ$ and $60\pm 7.5^\circ$. This is some of the wind directions showing larger areas with an increase in wind speed. Seeing this, it can be theorised whether the increase in wind speed is due to land effects or due to too few cases of the wind coming from these directions. These wind directions have fewer samples which is not unexpected as north to east are not a common wind direction as seen in Section 5.1.

When more than 500 or 600 samples are available, the increase in wind speed is not as pronounced as when having fewer samples as is the case in Figure 5.16.

Figure 5.16: The average relative difference with reference to EWP-1yr-1km-NoWF for wind direction (a) $20\pm 7.5^\circ$ with 223 samples, (b) $40\pm 7.5^\circ$ with 266 samples and (c) $60\pm 7.5^\circ$ with 218 samples. The arrow indicate wind direction. Legend: Upstream wind farms in simulation (\bullet), BOW (\bullet) and Shell Flats (\blacksquare).

The results presented in Section 5.2 regarding turbine power production and wind farm efficiency is investigated further in Figure 5.17. The objective is to see whether WRF can clarify or confirm the results in Section 5.2 for the SCADA analysis.

When the wind comes from south-west, close to 240° , it was seen that turbine D01 produced 50% more than turbine D08. Figure 5.17d shows how not the entire front row is hit by the wake from West of Duddon Sands. D08 is subject to a wind speed deficit of $5.5\pm 0.5\%$.

The wind farm efficiency for Barrow is at its lowest when the wind comes directly from West which can be seen for the WRF results in Figure 5.17e. All of Barrow is in the wake of the upstream wind farms and a decrease in wind speed across Barrow varies from $4.5\pm 0.5\%$ to $6.5\pm 0.5\%$. This is the most frequent wind direction, so even though the annual mean predicts that Barrow will experience a decrease in wind speed of $1.5\pm 0.5\%$, Barrow will most frequently be in a stronger wake.

When the wind comes from North-West (310°), the wind farm efficiency for BOW increased to be above 1. This is not due to Barrow being very efficient but rather Shell Flats being affected more by the wind farm wakes than Barrow. This is confirmed in Figure 5.17c and 5.17c. Shell

Flats is in the wind farm wake from Waley 1, Walney 2 and West of Duddon Sands with a decrease in wind speed up to $5.5 \pm 0.5\%$ whereas Barrow is in a weaker wake primarily caused by Ormonde. Barrow is predicted to mainly experience a decrease in wind speed of $2.5 \pm 0.5\%$, but a wind speed deficit up to $3.5 \pm 0.5\%$ is observed for the wind farm.

It should be noted that for all the wind directions shown in Figure 5.17 there are no areas indicating an increase in wind speed. The displayed wind directions all have more than 900 samples and have wind coming from the sea towards land.

Figure 5.17: The relative difference in wind speed with reference to EWP-1yr-1km-NoWF simulation for selected wind direction (a) and (d) $210 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 1681 samples, (b) and (e) $270 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 1413 samples and (c) and (f) $310 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 944 samples. The lower pane is an enlarged version of the upper. The arrow indicate the wind direction. Legend: Upstream wind farms in simulation (●), BOW (●) and Shell Flats (■).

5.4.2 Atmospheric Stability

WRF can output the inverse Obukhov length which is used to define the different stability classes: very unstable, unstable, near unstable, neutral, near stable, stable and very stable which are listed in Table 3.1.

In Figure 5.18, the most frequent stability class over the area is shown. Some values for the

inverse Obukhov length exceeded the upper or lower threshold for the stability classes, $-1/50$ and $1/10$ respectively. These data have not been included for Figure 5.18 which corresponds to 21.7% of the data.

The most frequent stability class in the Irish Sea is neutral. Near the coast, stable atmospheric conditions can also be seen, but it is mainly neutral with a few instances of unstable stability.

Figure 5.18: Most frequent stability classes.

The dependence on atmospheric stability for the wake is investigated for two directions: 270° and 310° . As reference for wind speed and direction, the Shell Flats cell will be used. Furthermore, the stability classes are collapsed so that unstable covers both very unstable and unstable, neutral covers near unstable, neutral and near stable and stable covers the two classes stable and very stable.

The result can be seen in Figure 5.19. The wake length depends on the stability with unstable conditions causing shorter wakes, 5.19a and 5.19d, and stable causing longer wakes, 5.19c and 5.19f.

When the wind comes from west, Barrow goes from experiencing mainly a $7\pm 1\%$ decrease in wind speed when in unstable conditions, $9\pm 1\%$ for neutral and up to $13\pm 1\%$ in stable conditions. If letting the wake length be defined by the lower limit of 2%, the wake length can be estimated to be 15 km for unstable, 29 km for neutral and 33 km for stable.

When the wind comes from north-west, the impact of atmospheric stability can be seen for Shell Flats, which is in a stronger wake as the stability goes from unstable to stable. Shell Flats is in a wind speed deficit of $5\pm 1\%$ in unstable, $7\pm 1\%$ in neutral and $9\pm 1\%$ in stable.

Figure 5.19: The relative difference in wind speed with reference to EWP-1yr-1km-NoWF simulation for selected wind direction and stability classes for 270° in the top row and 310° in the bottom row, where (a) unstable with 225 samples, (b) neutral with 413 samples, (c) stable with 68 samples, (d) unstable with 372 samples, (e) neutral with 240 samples and (f) stable with 48 samples. The arrow indicate the wind direction. Legend: Upstream wind farms in simulation (●), BOW (◐) and Shell Flats (■).

5.4.3 Summary

Using WRF enlightens how the conditions for Barrow are and how the upstream wind farm affect the area. Over the course of one year, it can be expected that Barrow will be in a wind speed deficit zone of $1.5 \pm 0.5\%$. The wake from the upstream wind farms are seen to be stronger depending on wind direction and atmospheric stability. When the wind comes from west, the prevailing wind direction, results in a decrease in wind speed up to $6.5 \pm 0.5\%$.

Figure 5.19 shows how a stronger and longer wake is associated with stable atmospheric condition. For stable atmospheric conditions and westerly wind, a decrease of $13 \pm 1\%$ in wind speed can be expected from Barrow.

From Figure 5.18, the most frequent stability class were predicted to be neutral. Hence, the strong wakes associated with stable atmospheric conditions are assumed not to be common.

WRF has been able to confirm some of the conditions that were theorised in Section 5.2 regarding the power production of turbines D01 and D08 and the wind farm efficiency. It is confirmed that when the wind comes from 240° , D01 will not be in the wind farm wake whereas D08 will be. When the wind comes from West, all of Barrow is in the wake from West of Duddon Sands which corresponds to when the smallest wind farm efficiency were seen in Section 5.2.

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5.5 EWP Validation

For validating the wind farm parametrisation, SCADA data from Barrow (BOW) will be used. The same analysis that was shown for only the SCADA will be performed using WRF results for the period 2014-2015, i.e. after the upstream wind farms have started operating. The analysis will focus on the limited range 120° - 360° since it is the effect of the upstream wind farms that is the objective.

5.5.1 Turbine Power Production

As in Section 5.2, the power production of turbine D01 normalised with turbine D08 will be considered. The wind speed criterion is based on the mean wind speed between the two. The wind direction is also based on a mean wind direction between the two time series. The power curve from the turbines in Barrow is used to estimate the power from WRF wind speeds. For the SCADA data, the mean wind direction from Barrow and the power production from the turbines are used.

In Figure 5.20, the power production of D01 normalised with D08 is shown. The simulation containing no turbines, EWP-1yr-1km-NoWF, is plotted for reference to verify that the two turbines ought to have the same power production if no upstream wind farms are present.

As Barrow wind farm is not in the WRF simulation, the internal wake effects cannot be seen from the WRF results which is evident from the figure as the SCADA data does show these, marked as grey areas. WRF follows the SCADA data until 240° . WRF predicts D01 to produce 32.9% more than D08 where SCADA observed 39.5%. After 240° , SCADA show that D01 will continue to produce more than D08 and at 246° D01 produces 50% more than D08. At the same time, WRF predicts that the power production of D01 and D08 will approach each other. Where SCADA show a maximum for D01, WRF predicts that D01 will produce 18.1% more than D08. The second peak in the SCADA data at 271° of 28% is not captured as well.

WRF manages to correctly estimate from which wind directions, D01 will produce more than D08. The magnitude of the power is underestimated, but is the same order of magnitude.

Figure 5.20: The power production of D01 normalised with D08.

5.5.2 Wind Farm Efficiency

The wind farm efficiency is computed from SCADA and WRF output. As a reference for wind speed and direction, Shell Flats measurements and the WRF time series extracted from the same location is used for SCADA and WRF respectively. The power curve for the turbines in Barrow (BOW) is used to estimate the power from WRF wind speeds.

The efficiency is shown in Figure 5.21 for free standing turbines (a) and all turbines (b). Coloured patches in the figures indicate various effects on the efficiency with respect to the simulation EWP-1yr-1km-WF. The simulation without turbines, EWP-1yr-1km-NoWF, is added as a reference. The efficiency does not correspond as well to SCADA as was the case in Figure 5.20.

It is confirmed, once again, that the reason for $1 < \eta_{SF}$ in the range 160° to 230° is not due to the upstream wind farms, as $1 < \eta_{SF}$ for both WRF simulations and the SCADA data.

WRF predicts a decrease in wind farm efficiency in the range 230° to 300° in both 5.21a and 5.21b which is a wider range than what is observed from SCADA (230° to 290°). For both analyses, free standing or all turbines, WRF follows the SCADA data in the range 230° to 300° until between 249° to 279° .

For the free standing turbines, SCADA showed the lowest efficiency to be 66.9% while WRF predicts a minimum efficiency of 82.6%. It corresponds to an overestimation of 23.8%.

When including all turbines, WRF predicts the lowest efficiency to be 83.8% in the range 230° to 300° where SCADA observes 63.1%, corresponding to an overestimation of 32.8%.

In the same range, a wind farm efficiency between 100% and 108%, both for free standing and all turbines, is predicted by WRF when not including the upstream wind farms.

In the range 300° to 340° , the simulations does not match SCADA well. EWP-1yr-1km-WF does predict, correctly, an increase in wind farm efficiency in Figure 5.21a (free turbines) but the peak is offset by 15° to the north. It is underestimated as 150.8% where SCADA shows 155.8%. In Figure 5.21b (all turbines), the wind farm efficiency is overestimated as 152% where SCADA shows a maximum efficiency of 124.8%. The peak is offset 25° to the north in WRF.

In Figure 5.22, the effect of adding the upstream turbines is evident. In the wind direction range where Barrow is subject to wind farm wakes (230° to 300°), the wind farm efficiency has changed with up to 22.9% for free standing turbines and 21.2% when using all the turbines. Even though the wind farm efficiency still is underestimated, it proves that the prediction of the performance of the wind farm has been improved.

Even though WRF underestimates the decrease in wind farm efficiency due to wakes from upstream wind farms, including the turbines with the EWP scheme improves the accuracy and prediction. WRF follows the same trend as SCADA and it gives an idea of what to expect in terms of wind farm efficiency and from which directions a decrease can be expected.

Figure 5.21: Wind farm efficiency from SCADA and WRF using (a) free standing turbines or (b) all turbines. Computed as a moving average for every degree with bin width $\pm 2.5^\circ$. The WRF simulations have been abbreviated to EWP-WF and EWP-NoWF for EWP-1yr-1km-WF and EWP-1yr-1km-NoWF respectively.

Figure 5.22: The relative difference between using WRF EWP scheme with and without turbines with reference to the simulation without turbines.

5.5.3 Summary

The WRF simulations are validated against SCADA data from BOW. When considering WRF in comparison with SCADA with respect to two turbines, WRF does accurately predict the range where they are affected by wind farm wakes which results in a decrease in power production for turbine D08 compared to D01. SCADA shows that D01 produces 50% more than D08 in this range whereas WRF predicts 32.9%.

The wind farm efficiency computed from SCADA and WRF is not as comparable. WRF does predict the range, 230° to 300° , where a decrease in wind farm efficiency can be expected due to wind farm wakes from the upstream wind farms, but also underestimates the impact of it. For free standing turbines, WRF predicts a minimum efficiency of 82.6% while SCADA shows an efficiency down to 66.7%. This is an improvement, however, from not including turbines with the EWP scheme, as the efficiency is predicted to be 22.9% lower than when not including the upstream turbines. This is close to what the SCADA data observed, where a decrease in efficiency of 28.3% was seen between the period with no upstream wind farms and the period after they were commissioned.

5.6 Annual Energy Production

The software WASP (12.2) is utilised to estimate the annual energy production (AEP) for Barrow. WRF is used as input for the generalised wind climate where both the simulation with the upstream wind farms and without will be used. In WASP, PARK2 is used as a wake model. The map over the Irish Sea for elevation and roughness is obtained from the Global Wind Atlas. The default settings for the wake decay coefficient is kept. The reference location for both wind climate and AEP is approximately in the centre of Barrow.

The resulting AEP and efficiency as a function of wind direction is shown in Figure 5.23. The gross AEP, 5.23a, remains approximately the same when using either wind climate until 240° . At first, EWP-WF is larger by 3.4% but then it decreases and a lower gross AEP is predicted for Barrow. At 270° the gross AEP is lower by 8.8% and at 300° it is 12.5%.

The net AEP, 5.23b, follows the same trend as the gross AEP with a larger net AEP of 3.3% at 240° and a smaller net AEP at 270° and 300° of 9.1% and 12.8% for EWP-WF.

The efficiency for Barrow when using either wind climate is almost the same except at 270° , where it is predicted that Barrow will have a lower efficiency when using EWP-WF climate of 95.64% compared to EWP-NoWF with 96.08%.

The tabulated values for Figure ref*fig:aep can be found in Appendix F.

In Table 5.6, the total gross and net AEP and efficiency is listed. The efficiency is the same for Barrow for both wind climate. The decrease in AEP is 3.8% and 3.9% for the gross and net respectively when using the EWP-WF climate.

Figure 5.23: WASP output for (a) AEP gross, (b) AEP net and (c) efficiency.

	EWP-NoWF	EWP-WF
Total AEP gross [MWh]	370,295.243	356,101.751
Total AEP net [MWh]	346,110.689	332,614.762
Efficiency [%]	93.47	93.4

Table 5.6: The total AEP for BOW when using the different wind climates.

5.6.1 Summary

The efficiency for Barrow when using either wind climate is the same except when the wind comes directly from West. The predicted net AEP decreases with 3.9% when using the EWP-WF climate compared to when using EWP-NoWF climate. The AEP is yet to be validated so the decrease in AEP cannot be confirmed. Seeing as WRF has underestimated the wind farm wake effects with 23.8% compared to SCADA observations, it can be assumed that the AEP is lower than what has been obtained here.

Conclusion

In this study, the impact of neighbouring wind farms on offshore wind resources was examined. Offshore wind energy continues to be installed in both existing and new markets. With the increased installed capacity, offshore wind farms have started being placed closer together. As wind farm wakes have been seen to extend as far as 75 km, their impact on wind resources cannot be neglected.

A site in the Irish Sea, where a cluster of wind farms are, was chosen as a case study. With the Weather Research & Forecasting (WRF) model, a wind resource assessment of the area where the wind farm Barrow is, were performed based for the period October 2014 through September 2015. To the west and north-west of Barrow are 4 upstream wind farms which were modelled with the Explicit Wake Parametrisation (EWP) in WRF. The wind farm owner provided wind farm data (SCADA) from Barrow and the upstream wind farms for validation of the wind resources. The annual energy production (AEP) was computed with the WRF wind climate by using the software Wind Atlas and Analysis and Application Program (WAsP).

Beside the wind resource assessment, the study also encompassed a review of the climatology in the Irish Sea, an analysis of wind farm wakes based on SCADA and a brief investigation of WRF grid resolution.

Regarding the wind resource assessment, using the EWP in WRF improved the predictions of the performance of Barrow compared with the available wind farm data. With respect to the wind farm efficiency, the impact of the wind farm wakes were underestimated. However, the impact of the wind farm wakes with respect to direction were accurately predicted.

WRF predicted a minimum wind farm efficiency of 82.6% due to wakes from upstream wind farms. In the same range of wind direction, SCADA observed an minimum efficiency of 66.7%. The annual energy production from WAsP was predicted to decrease with 3.9% when using the wind resource assessment including the upstream wind farm.

The maximum relative change in efficiency was 22.9% compared to the simulation which did not include the upstream wind farm for westerly winds. SCADA showed similarly a maximum change in efficiency of 28.3% compared to before the upstream wind farms were in operation. Even though the impacts of the wind farms are underestimated, the relative decrease in efficiency between WRF and SCADA are close.

From the climatology, it was confirmed that the prevailing wind is from the west, the same direction as the upstream wind farms from Barrow. SCADA showed that it was for westerly winds, the lowest wind farm efficiency occurred. For the front row turbines facing the wind farm wake, the power production of the turbines were seen to differ in SCADA data. The difference was up to a 50% increase between two front row turbines for westerly wind. WRF predicted the same behaviour but underestimated the impact of the upstream wind farm and predicted the turbine to produce 32.9% more instead of 50%.

Not only wind direction, but also atmospheric stability was predicted to have an impact on the wind farm wakes. For the prevailing wind, a stronger wake was seen for stable atmospheric conditions than for unstable and neutral. WRF predicted neutral atmospheric conditions to be the most frequent so the strong wakes under stable conditions should not be experienced often. The impact of atmospheric stability has not been validated.

Even though WRF underestimated the impact of the upstream wind farms, utilising the EWP scheme improved the predictions of the performance and it can therefore be recommended.

Subsequent studies could involve validating the wake length dependent on atmospheric stability, or validating the wind farm wakes with other measurement sources than wind farm data. The advantage in this project was the access to wind farm data which allows the WRF results to be validated in space as well as time. There are, however, uncertainties and challenges in using wind farm data. WRF computes wind speeds which are converted into power using a turbine power curve in order to compare with wind farm data. Converting either wind speed to power or power to wind speed via a power curve includes uncertainties. It would be preferable to compare WRF outputs with direct measurements of wind speed from e.g. meteorological masts or lidar while still having the advantage of several data sources distributed in space.

The Irish Sea

An enlarged version of the figures shown in Figure 1.2.

Figure A.1: Larger version of figure shown in Figure 1.2

Figure A.2: Larger version of figure shown in Figure 1.2

Shell Flats 2011-2012 Data Quality Control

The raw data from the difference in wind speed between BOW, the sonic anemometer and the wind vanes on the SE and NW boom.

Figure B.1: The difference in measured wind direction between met mast instruments and the computed BOW wind direction, where (a) is BOW minus ultra sonic anemometer, (b) is BOW minus wind vane at NW boom and (c) is BOW minus wind vane at SE boom.

Shell Flats 2014-2015 Data Quality Control

(a)

(b)

Figure C.1: The difference in measured wind direction between met mast instruments and the computed BOW wind direction, where (a) is BOW minus wind vane at NW boom and (b) is BOW minus wind vane at NW boom.

Figure C.2: The wind speed fraction with respect to wind direction for (a) u_{50mSE}/u_{50mNW} , (b) u_{70mSE}/u_{70mNW} and (c) u_{80mSE}/u_{82mTop} .

WRF Grid Resolution: Wind speed and direction in Shell Flats cell

Figure D.1: The (a) wind speed and (b) direction for simulations without upstream wind farms in the Shell Flats cell.

WRF Mean Wind Field

The relative difference in mean wind field for every $10 \pm 7.5^\circ$.

Figure E.1: The relative difference in wind speed with reference to EWP-1yr-1km-NoWF simulation for selected wind direction (a) $0 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 375 samples, (b) $10 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 308 samples, (c) $20 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 223 samples, (d) $30 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 204 samples, (e) $40 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 266 samples and (f) $50 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 216 samples. The arrow indicate the wind direction. Legend: Upstream wind farms in simulation (●), BOW (◐) and Shell Flats (■).

Figure E.2: The relative difference in wind speed with reference to EWP-1yr-1km-NoWF simulation for selected wind direction (a) $60 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 218 samples, (b) $70 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 282 samples, (c) $80 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 335 samples, (d) $90 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 543 samples, (e) $100 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 613 samples, (f) $110 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 603 samples, (g) $120 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 604 samples, (h) $130 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 707 samples and (i) $140 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 804 samples. The arrow indicate the wind direction. Legend: Upstream wind farms in simulation (●), BOW (●) and Shell Flats (■).

Figure E.3: The relative difference in wind speed with reference to EWP-1yr-1km-NoWF simulation for selected wind direction (a) $150 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 806 samples, (b) $160 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 750 samples, (c) $170 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 687 samples, (d) $180 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 551 samples, (e) $190 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 545 samples, (f) $200 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 512 samples, (g) $210 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 689 samples, (h) $220 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 1172 samples and (i) $230 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 1691 samples. The arrow indicate the wind direction. Legend: Upstream wind farms in simulation (●), BOW (●) and Shell Flats (■).

Figure E.4: The relative difference in wind speed with reference to EWP-1yr-1km-NoWF simulation for selected wind direction (a) $240 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 1681 samples, (b) $250 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 1389 samples, (c) $260 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 1374 samples, (d) $270 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 1413 samples, (e) $280 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 1316 samples, (f) $290 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 1096 samples, (g) $300 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 1017 samples, (h) $310 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 944 samples and (i) $320 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 761 samples. The arrow indicate the wind direction. Legend: Upstream wind farms in simulation (\bullet), BOW (\circ) and Shell Flats (\blacksquare).

Figure E.5: The relative difference in wind speed with reference to EWP-1yr-1km-NoWF simulation for selected wind direction (a) $330 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 705 samples, (b) $340 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 795 samples and (c) $350 \pm 7.5^\circ$ with 768 samples. The arrow indicate the wind direction. Legend: Upstream wind farms in simulation (●), BOW (●) and Shell Flats (■).

Annual Energy Production

The values in the table corresponds to Figure 5.23.

	AEP gross [MWh]		AEP netto [MWh]		Efficiency [%]	
	EWP-NoWF	EWP-WF	EWP-NoWF	EWP-WF	EWP-NoWF	EWP-WF
Sector 1 (0°)	7225.851	6411.151	6588.042	5852.064	91.17	91.28
Sector 2 (30°)	2703.757	2658.923	2457.961	2425.272	90.91	91.21
Sector 3 (60°)	3777.805	3506.220	3342.590	3091.972	88.48	88.19
Sector 4 (90°)	8185.494	7991.753	7362.013	7180.642	89.94	89.85
Sector 5 (120°)	22904.236	22190.776	19788.292	19151.675	86.4	86.3
Sector 6 (150°)	30956.294	30739.954	28995.101	28779.121	93.66	93.62
Sector 7 (180°)	23755.397	23044.563	22510.408	21845.717	94.76	94.8
Sector 8 (210°)	50059.391	49220.125	47644.488	46833.238	95.18	95.15
Sector 9 (240°)	80481.444	83228.606	77036.249	79610.151	95.72	95.65
Sector 10 (270°)	73599.238	67241.447	70714.515	64306.790	96.08	95.64
Sector 11 (300°)	41563.828	36354.302	36598.895	31913.435	88.05	87.78
Sector 12 (330°)	25082.452	23513.913	23072.135	21624.689	91.99	91.97

Table F.1: Annual energy production per sector.

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